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**BATCH CULTURES OF NATIVE STRAINS OF
NITZSCHIA PALEA FROM THE CANARY ISLANDS:
GROWTH MONITORING USING DIRECT AND INDIRECT METHODS**

MASTERARBEIT

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ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

In der Literatur sind mehrere Methoden zur Überwachung des Wachstums von Mikroalgen im Labor beschrieben. Direkte Messungen über die Zelldichte und Biomasseausbeute gelten als die zuverlässigsten Methoden. Indirekte Methoden beruhen im Allgemeinen auf bestimmten Parametern, die als Folge der phototrophen Aktivität gemessen werden können. Während indirekte Methoden zweifellos weniger zeitaufwändig sind, muss ihre Relevanz spezifisch für die Art und die verwendeten Versuchsbedingungen bewertet werden.

In dieser Studie bestand das Hauptziel darin, die Relevanz von Messungen der optischen Dichte (OD) und der basalen Fluoreszenz (F_0) für die Überwachung des Wachstums von Batch-Kulturen der benthischen Kieselalge *Nitzschia palea* zu testen. Weitere Experimente zur Bestimmung der Photosynthese-Effizienz, der Menge und Zusammensetzung der Biomasse, zum Lipidgehalt und zum Fettsäureprofil wurden mit dem Ziel durchgeführt, den optimalen Erntezeitpunkt für biotechnologische Anwendungen zu bestimmen.

Drei kanarische Stämme von *Nitzschia palea* (BEA 0255B, BEA 0256B und BEA 0392B) wurden in dreifachen 1 L Erlenmeyerkolben mit 270 ml FDMed-Medium 26 Tage lang bei einer anfänglichen Zelldichte von $1,3 \times 10^5$ Zellen $\text{ml}^{-1} \pm 27$ % (RSD) kultiviert. Die Biomasse wurde geerntet und an zwei Punkten der Wachstumskurve weiter analysiert: an Tag 9 (exponentielle Wachstumsphase) und an Tag 26 (stationäre Wachstumsphase).

Die drei *Nitzschia palea* Stämme zeigten ihre maximalen Wachstumsraten (μ_{max}) zwischen Tag 4 und 7 ($0,21 - 0,29 \text{ Tag}^{-1}$) und traten am Tag 17 in die stationäre Wachstumsphase ein, wobei eine durchschnittliche Konzentration von $1,5 \times 10^6$ Zellen $\text{ml}^{-1} \pm 11$ % (RSD) beibehalten wurde. Ein Vergleich zwischen Zelldichte, OD und F_0 wurde in derselben Analyse unter Verwendung der Daten jedes Replikats der drei Stämme durchgeführt.

Die Relevanz von OD- und F_0 -Messungen wurde während der exponentiellen Phase gezeigt, da beide in einem linearen Regressionsmodell positiv mit der Zelldichte korrelierten (Tage 4 – 17, $R^2 > 0,87$, $n = 45$). Während der stationären Phase (Tage 17 – 26, $R^2 < 0,46$, $n = 45$) wurde eine schwache lineare Korrelation gefunden.

Die Biomasseausbeute der drei Stämme lagen in einem Bereich von $3,1 - 3,8 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$ Trockengewicht (TG), ohne signifikante Unterschiede zwischen den Stämmen oder den Wachstumsphasen.

An Tag 9 lag der Lipidgehalt zwischen 9 und 11 % TG, während der Lipidgehalt am Tag 26 zwischen 6 und 8 % TG lag. Der Lipidgehalt aller drei *N. palea*-Stämme war an Tag 9 im Vergleich zu Tag 26 geringfügig höher, jedoch nicht signifikant und im Vergleich zu anderen Studien insgesamt niedrig.

Die vorläufigen Studien zur Fettsäurezusammensetzung eröffnen potenzielle Anwendungen für die *N. palea* Stämme in verschiedenen biotechnologischen Bereichen, einschließlich der Nutrazeutik- und Aquakultursektoren.

SUMMARY

Several methods for monitoring the growth of microalgae in the laboratory have been described in the literature. Direct measurements, such as cell density and biomass yield, are considered as the most reliable methods. Indirect methods generally rely on specific parameters that can be measured as a consequence of the phototrophic activity. While indirect methods are undoubtedly less time-consuming, their relevance needs to be evaluated case by case for the species and the experimental conditions used.

In this study, the main objective was to test the relevance of optical density (OD) and basal fluorescence (F_0) measurements for monitoring the growth of batch cultures of the benthic diatom *Nitzschia palea*. Further experiments addressing photosynthetic efficiency, biomass weight and composition, lipid content and fatty acid profile were conducted with the aim of determining the optimal harvesting time for biotechnological applications.

Three Canarian strains of *Nitzschia palea* (BEA 0255B, BEA 0256B and BEA 0392B) were cultured in triplicate 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks with 270 mL FDMed medium for 26 days at an initial cell density of 1.3×10^5 cells $\text{mL}^{-1} \pm 27\%$ (RSD). Biomass was harvested and further analyzed at two points of the growth curve, one corresponding to the exponential phase (day 9) and the other corresponding to the stationary phase (day 26).

The three strains showed their maximum growth rates (μ_{max}) between days 4 and 7 ($0.21 - 0.29 \text{ day}^{-1}$), and entered the stationary phase at day 17, maintaining an average concentration of 1.5×10^6 cells $\text{mL}^{-1} \pm 11\%$ (RSD). Comparison between cell density, OD and F_0 was performed using the data of each replicate of the three strains in the same analysis.

The relevance of OD and F_0 measurements was demonstrated during the exponential phase, as they both positively correlated with cell density in a linear regression model (days 4 – 17, $R^2 > 0.87$, $n = 45$). Very poor linear correlation was found during the stationary phase (days 17 – 26, $R^2 < 0.46$, $n = 45$).

The biomass yields of the three strains were comprised in a range of $3.1 - 3.8 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$ dry weight (DW), without significant differences between strains or growth phases.

At day 9, lipid content represented between 9 and 11 % DW, whereas at day 26, lipid content was between 6 and 8 % DW. The lipid content in all three *N. palea* strains was slightly higher at day 9 compared to day 26, but not significant, and overall low compared to other studies. The preliminary studies on fatty acid composition opens up potential applications for these strains in different biotechnological areas, including nutraceutical and aquaculture sectors.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

DHA	docosahexaenoic acid
μ_{\max}	maximum growth rate
A	absorbance
ANOVA	analysis of variance
ATP	adenosin triphosphate
BHT	butylated hydroxytoluene
CD _f	final cell density
CD _i	initial cell density
cf	confer
Chl <i>a</i>	chlorophyll <i>a</i>
D	day
DI	dissipation energy
DP	datapoint
DT	doubling time
DT _{min}	minimum doubling time
DW	dry weight
EPA	eicosapentaenoic acid
ET	electron transport energy
exp.	exponential
F ₀	basal fluorescence
FAs	fatty acids
FDMed	Freshwater medium optimized for diatoms
FM	maximal fluorescence intensity
Fv/Fm	maximum light utilisation efficiency of PSII (dark adapted state)
GC-MS	gaschromatograph with massspectrometer
LD	light:dark
LED	Light-emitting diode
LYO	lyophilized
MQ	milli Q
MUFAs	monounsaturated fatty acids
N	number
N. palea	nitzschia palea
NADP	Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate
NADPH	reduced form of NADP

NPQ	Non-photochemical quenching
OD	optical density
OD ₆₈₀	optical density measured at 680 nm
OD ₇₅₀	optical density measured at 750 nm
PAM	Pulse-Amplitude-Modulation
PQ	free plastoquinone
PS _I	photosystem I
PS _{II}	photosystem II
PUFAs	polyunsaturated fatty acids
Q _A	plastoquinone A
Q _B	plastoquinone B
RC	reaction center
Ref	reference
RSD	percent relative standard deviation
SD	standard deviation
sp	species
stat.	stationary
TAGs	triacylglycerols
TG	Trockengewicht
TR	trapping of excitation energy
UV	ultraviolet
V	volume
v/v	volume/volume
VIS	Visible spectrophotometry
w/	with
w/o	without
X	mean

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1. INTRODUCTION

Fast globalization and industrialization have widely affected the ecosystem and thus drove scientists to reach out for alternatives and more sustainable resources.

The phylogenetic diversity of microalgae results in a great multifariousness in their chemical composition, turning them into important biological resources for biotechnological applications.

Nowadays, one of the pressing issues is the development of renewable energy sources in order to reduce the dependence on fossil fuels. To date, almost 95 % of the transportation industry relies on non-renewable energy sources (Rodrigue & Notteboom 2013). Microalgae may serve as carbon-neutral bioenergy thanks to their high content in lipids and carbohydrates.

In the nutraceutical field, microalgae also find use as source of important nutrients in the food and feed industries, such as the omega-3 fatty acids (FAs) eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA). The source of these FAs still relies on the fish industry, which presents some issues. The main ones are ocean pollution and fluctuation in the quality of fish oil, which is influenced by seasonal variation that affects its biochemical composition (Alves Martins et al. 2013).

The microalgae class of diatoms has long been proposed for industrial applications since some species can continuously grow with an average of 132 MT of dry diatoms ha⁻¹ per year (Wang & Seibert 2017) and contain a fat amount of 40 % up to 80 % of dry weight (Deuticke et al. 1949, Kather 1950, Harder & von Wich 1953). Nowadays, the prospect of industrialization of diatoms has considerably increased in accordance with the growing knowledge in several fields such as microscopy and metabarcoding, as well as the technological advances in analytical and genetic tools. Altogether, these aspects lead to more cost-effective cultivation, harvesting and downstream processing. Despite this, the research in this area is still very poor compared to industrial applications of other microbes such as bacteria, which has exponentially increased since the beginning of the millennium. Very few diatom species are currently used for production of biotechnologically relevant products (Lebeau & Robert 2003). Considering their wide biodiversity and interesting biochemical

composition, diatoms need to be further studied in order to foster their exploitation in various sectors of the industry (Sharma et al. 2021).

The work presented in this Master's thesis was performed in the facilities of the Spanish Bank of Algae (Banco Español de Algas, BEA) under the supervision of Dr. Francesco Pisapia. The BEA is a national R&D service of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) managed by the Canarian Science and Technology Park Foundation (Fundación Parque Científico Tecnológico, FPCT). The main objectives of the BEA concern the isolation, characterization, conservation and supply of microalgae and cyanobacteria, as well as the development of cultivation techniques and the study of their applications from a scientific-technological point of view. The BEA is listed in the World Data Centre for Microorganisms (WFCC-MIRCEN) under registration number 837. Also, it has been a member of the European Culture Collections' Organisation (ECCO) since 2001, and of the World Federation for Culture Collections (WFCC) since 2003. The BEA is accredited as an international authority for the deposit of microorganisms in accordance with the Treaty of Budapest by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) before the Government of Spain. To date, the BEA collection possesses more than 1700 clonal strains, most of them isolated from the Macaronesian region, representing unique genetic resources for potential application in biotechnology.

The here-present Master's thesis contributes to the working package 3 of Genetics in the framework of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) NewTechAqua (NTA) project (H2020-EU.3.2.3.2, grant agreement ID: 862658). The main goal of the H2020 NewTechAqua project is to expand and diversify European aquaculture production of finfish, molluscs and microalgae by developing and validating technologically-advances, resilient and sustainable applications (www.newtechaqua.eu). In the framework of NTA, the BEA focuses on the development of microalgae strains with higher yields of biomass and/or target metabolites for aquafeed applications, e.g. high-value fatty acids. The approach for such development consists in genetic recombination through classical breeding, i.e. controlled sexual reproduction. Among the major classes of microalgae, diatoms are almost unique in having a diplontic life cycle, which means that their life cycle includes a phase of sexual reproduction. In particular, heterothallic diatoms are considered as particularly suitable for the NTA project, since they offer a better control on the sexual encounters experimentally (Pisapia et al., 2021a, 2021b).

Among the heterothallic diatoms available at the BEA Collection, *Nitzschia palea* was one of the species of interest selected for the NTA project, both for its life cycle (Bagmet et al. 2020) and lipid production (Opute 1974, Abdel-Hamid et al. 2013, Hassan et al. 2013).

In this Master's thesis, three native strains of *Nitzschia palea* isolated from the Canary Islands were cultivated and monitored in batch cultures in order to study their growth and lipid production over time.

The main objective of this study was to test the reliability of indirect methods for growth monitoring of this species. Growth monitoring is an unavoidable requirement for the cultivation of microalgae with biotechnological interest, since the obtention of a high quality biomass (e.g. high amounts of lipids and industrially interesting fatty acids) is strongly related to the physiological state of the cultures. The use of spectrophotometry or fluorometry instruments are indicated in the literature as indirect methods for cell density estimation and represent a way to accelerate growth monitoring processes. It remained to be evaluated the applicability of such methodologies at the BEA laboratory for the species of interest *N. palea*.

Another objective of this Master's thesis was to obtain biomass from *N. palea* cultures at different physiological states, and compare biomass yields, lipid contents and fatty acid profiles. Quantification of the biomass and subsequent biochemical analyses are essential to understand the potential of a particular species (or strain) for biotechnological applications. Comparison of the findings from this study with the literature contributes to widen knowledge on *N. palea* species and head towards further developments and future perspectives.

The Master's thesis is divided into six chapters:

- Chapter two follows the introduction and describes the **Theoretical Background**, where the world of microalgae and their applications are introduced, as well as more detailed information on the diatom species *Nitzschia palea*.
- Chapter three, **Materials and Methods**, addresses the description of the strains, the experimental plan, the culture system, the materials and the methods used for growth monitoring and biomass characterization.

- Chapter four concerns the **Results** of this study, which depicts the growth of the strains over time, the comparison between direct and indirect counting methods, the photosynthetic efficiency and the biomass characterization.
- Chapter five addresses the **Discussion** section, where the results of this study are compared with previous findings in the literature.
- Finally, Chapter six resumes the **Conclusions and Perspectives** of this study, including the suggestion of future approaches for optimization and further development of the presented experiments.

Part of the work included in this Master's thesis served as scientific contributions (virtual poster presentation) at two international conferences held online, referenced below:

- **Merse, A.**, Sánchez Humayor, M., Medina Alcaraz, C., Martel Quintana, A., Gómez Pinchetti, J. L. and Pisapia, F. (2021). Direct versus indirect methods for growth measurements in batch cultures of *Nitzschia palea*. 5th Young Algaeneers Symposium (YAS). Online.
- Pisapia, F., **Merse, A.**, Sánchez Humayor, M., Medina Alcaraz, C., Martel Quintana, A. and Gómez Pinchetti, J. L. (2021). Relevance of indirect methods for monitoring the growth of *Nitzschia palea* in batch cultures. 10th Algal Biomass, Biofuels and Bioproducts International Conference (Algal BBB 2021). Online.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. MICROALGAE AND THEIR APPLICATIONS

Microalgae is a large and diverse group of prokaryotic and eukaryotic autotrophic organisms (Li et al. 2008), part of the phytoplankton. They are unicellular species and can be found in freshwater, seawater and hypersaline environments, living in the water column or on sediments (Thurman 1997). Microalgae are primary producers in the trophic chain of aquatic environment and play a vital role in the stability of marine ecosystems.

The phylogenetic diversity of microalgae results in a great diversity in their chemical composition, turning them into important biological resources with high potential for biotechnological applications. Their unicellular organization leads to higher capacity for growth and biomass generation compared to higher plants: since they do not need to take root or generate reproductive structures, they can multiply in a matter of hours (Zullaikah et al. 2019). Their short life cycle and metabolic plasticity give the opportunity to modify their biochemical metabolism and cellular composition through variation of culture conditions (Malapascua et al. 2014). Altogether, these aspects make microalgae more interesting for biotechnological applications than any terrestrial crop plant.

Microalgae are a natural source of protein, carbohydrates, lipids and other bioactive compounds. Among these, polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) are considered high-value products with potential applications in the pharmaceutical, nutraceutical and cosmeceutical industries (Madeira et al. 2017, Specht et al. 2010, Subhadra 2010, 2011). Microalgae also find application in the biofuel production (Chisti & Yan 2011, Jones & Mayfield 2012, Subhadra, 2010, 2011), bioremediation of wastewater (Benemann 2008, Das et al. 2019) and manufacture of fertilizers and animal feeding in the agro-industrial sector (Camacho et al. 2019, Madeira et al. 2017, Subhadra, 2010, 2011).

Furthermore, several microalgae, especially dinoflagellates and cyanobacteria, are source of bioactive compounds with interesting properties for drug development in the pharmaceutical

sector. Some species are toxic and considerably affect seafood safety. However, the unique structures and diverse functionalities of the biotoxins make them promising pharmacological effectors in the biomedical and toxicological fields (Assunção et al. 2017).

The application and commercialisation of microalgae is not something new. It all started about 75 years ago with their use in wastewater treatments and the mass production of strains of *Chlorella* and *Dunaliella* (Abdel-Raouf et al., 2012). Nowadays, the microalgae genera *Chlorella* and *Arthrospira* (i.e. spirulina) are widely known in the nutraceutical sector as so-called “superfood”, and have long been produced commercially.

2.2. DIATOMS

Diatoms (*Bacillariophyceae*) are a major component of phytoplankton. They are unicellular organisms and can be found both in fresh and marine waters, as well as in wastewaters and humid soil (Scalco 2014). Diatoms are either planktonic, i.e. living in the water column, or epibenthic, i.e. growing on sand, stones or aquatic vegetation.

Diatoms are the most diverse group within the microalgae, with more than 1000 genera known to date (Worlds register of marine species, 2020) and more than 200,000 known species (Mann & Vanormelingen 2013). Genera and species show a broad morphological, physiological and ecological heterogeneity. These characteristics may be consequence of the chimeric nature of their genomes, produced by the incorporation of genes from their endosymbiotic ancestors, as well as by horizontal gene transfer from marine bacteria (Bowler et al. 2010).

The distinctive feature of diatoms compared to other phytoplanktonic groups is their characteristic siliceous cell wall, the frustule. The frustule is made up of two slightly unequal valves that fit together like the lid on a box: the epitheca and hypotheca (Figure 1) (Scalco 2014).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the structure of a diatom cell wall, the silica frustule, composed of two valves, an epitheca and a hypotheca (Kröger & Wetherbee 2000).

Diatoms can be classified into two main groups based on their shape: centric and pennate diatoms (Figure 2) (Medlin & Kaczmarska 2004).

Figure 2. Illustrations of (a) a centric diatom, and (b) a pennate diatom (Gillard, 2009).

As autotrophic protists, diatoms influence the ocean ecology and biogeochemistry in many ways, mainly through the carbon and silicon cycles. They control the biogenic cycling of silicon in the world's oceans by incorporating silicon of dissolved silicic acid into their cell wall (Tréguer et al. 1995). Furthermore, they can fix large amounts of carbon dioxide and converge them into carbohydrates synthesis. Consequently, diatoms are at the base of marine food chains, serving as a nutriment source for higher trophic levels (Kociolek & Seckbach 2011). Approximately 40 % of the organic matter generated annually in the ocean by photosynthetic production can be traced back to diatoms and about one-fifth of the photosynthesis on earth is carried out by them (Nelson et al. 1995). All in all, diatoms are considered to be one of the most ecologically important groups of phytoplankton and one of the largest components of marine biomass (Smetacek 1999, Leblanc et al. 2012, Brun et al. 2015).

The ability of diatoms to grow in several natural environments, as well as their abundance, ubiquitous presence and adaptability in a wide range of climatic and geographical assets, are some of the reasons why they are suitable candidates for biotechnological applications (Jin & Agusti 2018). Some examples of biotechnological applications of diatoms are reviewed by Sharma et al. (2021) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Schematic representation of different applications of diatoms in the industry (Sharma et al. 2021).

2.2.1. Life cycle

Among the eukaryotic algae, diatoms constitute the phylogenetic group with the richest diversity in terms of genera and species. Nevertheless, most of them conserve a diplontic life cycle associated with cell size variations (Mann 1993).

Life cycle of most diatoms articulates into two main phases: **(1)** a prolonged **vegetative phase**, lasting months to years, characterized by mitotic reproduction accompanied by gradual cell size reduction; and **(2)** a comparatively short **sexual phase**, lasting days to weeks, characterized by meiotic reproduction and a complex size-restitution process leading to the formation of new vegetative cells. The vegetative stage interacts in a unique way with

the sexual stage due to the cell size reduction, according to the MacDonald-Pfitzer rule (Edlund & Stoermer 1997).

- (1) When a diatom cell divides vegetatively, two new hypovalves are built inside the parental valves, creating a daughter cell that is smaller than the parental one (Chepurnov et al. 2004). This process is repeated in every single cell division, resulting in a gradual decrease in the cell size of a clonal population (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Cell size reduction of a diatom cell due to subsequent mitotic divisions (Scalco 2014).

- (2) Sexual reproduction of diatoms generally include meiosis, gametogenesis, fertilization and formation of a specialized zygote (auxospore) (Scalco 2014). Sexualisation only occurs when cell size reaches a critical threshold, and is an obligate requirement to avoid the population to die. Size thresholds for sexualisation are the so-called “cardinal points”, and are species-specific. The auxospores generated from sexual reproduction expand until reaching the maximal cell size and start a new vegetative phase of the life cycle.

The sexual phase of diatoms is extremely important in their life cycle. It does not only give the opportunity to restore the maximum initial cell size, ensuring their survival, but also allows the generation of biodiversity through genetic recombination. Most diatoms are obligate sexual organisms, and clonal lineages have limited or no ability to maintain themselves for more than a few years (Chepurnov et al. 2004). Knowledge on the species-specific cardinal points plays an important role for the development of methods for maintaining diatoms in cultures (Bagmet et al. 2020).

Two different sexual patterns can be distinguished between the two main groups of diatoms, centric and pennate (Scalco 2014). Centric diatoms are mostly homothallic, which means that both male and female gametes can be produced by a given monoclonal strain. They undergo the so-called “oogamous sexual reproduction”, producing large, immotile eggs and flagellated, motile sperms. In contrast, pennate diatoms are generally heterothallic, which means that a given monoclonal strain belongs to a defined “sex gender” (or “mating type”) and is capable of producing one type of gametes only. The gametes are generally non-flagellated and motility scarce, so they need to be close enough to allow conjugation (Scalco 2014, Gillard 2009). As a consequence, most centric diatoms are capable of self-fertilization, while pennate diatoms generally need to undergo cross-fertilization (Chepurnov et al. 2004).

2.2.2. *Nitzschia palea*

Nitzschia palea is a widely distributed diatom species of moderately motile and benthic character (Guiry 2002), living in freshwater ecosystems and frequently found in hypertrophic, lotic and lentic waters, in both epilithic and epipelagic assemblages (Sonneman et al. 1999). Finlay et al. 2002 defined the *N. palea* taxon as a ubiquitous, ecologically tolerant and generalist diatom. Moreover, this species has been described as a good environmental indicator of highly eutrophic conditions and of heavy metal pollution (Bere & Tundisi 2011).

N. palea is a morphological diverse species, with valves variable in shape and size (Figure 5). The shape of their valve can be narrow/broadly linear – lanceolate or linear, with narrowly elongated, pointedly rounded, subcapitate or capitate ends (Figure 5). Their length ranges from 15 and 70 μm , with an average of 32 – 35 μm , and their width ranges from 2.5 to 5 μm , with an average of 4 – 4.5 μm (Sonneman et al. 1999).

Figure 5. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) pictures of the valves of 25 *N. palea* clones (Sonneman et al. 1999). All micrographs are in the same magnification (scale bar = 5 μm).

Furthermore, they are not only heterogeneous with respect to their morphology (Trobajo et al. 2009) but also in their molecular sequence (Rimet et al. 2014). Their diversity in the molecular sequences has even led to hypothesize the existence of cryptic species within *N. palea* (Trobajo et al. 2009, Trobajo et al. 2010).

The life cycle of *N. palea* has recently been described by Bagmet et al. (2020). As most diatoms, life cycles consists of different stages according to cell size: **(a) pre-reproductive stage**, at maximum cell length (between 40 and 50 μm); **(b) reproductive stage**, at cell length between 15 and 30 μm , and **(c) post-reproductive stage**, at cell length < 15 μm (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Valves' morphology for 13 *Nitzschia palea* clones and their respective life cycle phase according to cell length: a) pre-reproductive, b) reproductive, c) post-reproductive (Bagmet et al. 2020). Scale bar = 10 μm.

Nitzschia palea was included in some of the earliest studies on fat accumulation by diatoms, reaching a lipid content up to 80 % dry weight (Denffer 1948, 1949; Opute 1974). Based on its lipid content, more recent studies proposed *N. palea* as a promising source of raw material for biodiesel production (Abdel-Hamid et al. 2013, Hassan et al. 2013).

2.3. CULTIVATION OF MICROALGAE

In the microalgae industry, the productivity of selected species of interest need to be optimized using efficient cultivation techniques and experimental conditions. Microalgae cultivation in artificial environments generated in the laboratory can improve biomass densities with respect to their natural habitat, through adjustment of culture conditions to specific needs (Malapascua et al. 2014).

Some of the most important culture conditions to take into account when cultivating microalgae in the laboratory are: temperature, salinity, nutrient supply (culture medium), light intensity and photoperiod, pH and turbulence (Goldman et al. 1982).

Culture media are prepared using distilled or ultrapure water in the case of freshwater microorganisms, and natural or artificial seawater in the case of marine microorganisms. Enrichment of culture media consists of the addition of macronutrients and micronutrients. Essential macronutrients for microalgae are carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, sulphur, calcium and magnesium. Micronutrient requirement consists of trace metals and vitamins. Trace metals include iron, boron, manganese, copper, molybdenum, vanadium, cobalt, nickel, selenium and, for diatom culturing, silicate as well (Vargas Arigony et al. 2013). Vitamins are also part of most of the culture media recipes, and generally include thiamine (B1), cyanocobalamin (B12) and sometimes biotin (Vargas Arigony et al. 2013).

The most common culture systems used in the laboratory are batch cultures, fed-batch cultures and continuous cultures (Figure 7). In batch cultures, all the nutrients are added at the beginning of the cultivation along with microalgae inoculum, without any other nutrient supply at a later stage (Devasya 2017). When culture conditions are suitable for a given microalgae, nutrients are efficiently uptaken, fostering primary metabolism, cell division and growth. As time passes, in batch cultures nutrients are progressively consumed, cells undergo nutrient limitation and starvation, and the cultivation suffers a decline. In order to maintain the culture alive, it is necessary to regularly transfer the cells into new culture vessels with fresh medium. In fed-batch cultures and continuous cultures, microalgae are semi-continuously or continuously fed with nutrients, so that they never experience nutrient limitation and decline. Fed-batch cultures receive nutrient supplies as only manipulation, while in continuous cultures, part of the biomass is also removed (harvested product) along with nutrient addition.

Figure 7. Schematic representation of the most common culture systems used in the laboratory for microalgae: (a) batch culture, (b) fed-batch culture, and (c) continuous culture (Rashid et al. 2012).

A standard batch cultivation generally starts with a low inoculum of around 0.1 – 0.2 g L⁻¹ of dry matter (Franco 2013). Batch cultivation leads to a standard growth curve with four phases (Figure 8): **(1) lag phase**, where the cells adapt to the cultivation conditions and there is rarely any growth; **(2) exponential phase**, where sufficient nutrients are available and cells proliferate with a maximal growth rate; **(3) stationary phase**, when nutrient limitation starts to slow down the growth and maximal cell concentration is reached and **(4) death**, where nutrients are exhausted and the maximal biomass concentration cannot be maintained any longer (Franco 2013).

Figure 8. Growth curve of microalgae in batch culture systems over time (Mara 2003, modified).

2.4. GROWTH MONITORING OF MICROALGAE

Growth monitoring is an unavoidable requirement for the cultivation of microalgae with biotechnological interest, since the obtention of a high quality biomass is strongly related to the physiological state of microalgae cultures.

The study of microalgal growth in the laboratory generally include biomass amount and/or cell density assessment over time.

The amount of produced biomass can be expressed in terms of fresh (FW) or dry (DW) weight. Dry weight is more accurate than wet weight, because water content (moisture) can change depending on conditions and affect the measurements. Furthermore, dry weight can give a more detailed description of the biomass composition, consisting of an organic

fraction and inorganic fraction. The latter can be quantified through ash content determination.

Cell density can be directly measured using cell counting chambers under a microscope, or estimated using indirect techniques. Indirect techniques generally rely on specific parameters that can be measured as a consequence of the phototrophic activity, such as light interaction with pigments. Examples of indirect methods for cell density estimation include the spectrophotometric determination of chlorophyll *a* (chl *a*) absorbance (optical density) and the fluorometric determination of chl *a* fluorescence (basal fluorescence). Although somewhat less reliable, indirect methods present the advantage of being less time consuming than direct ones.

2.4.1. Direct methods

2.4.1.1. Dry biomass

The dry biomass of microalgae can be obtained through several techniques, some of them being the following: rotary drying, spray drying, vacuum-shelf drying, oven drying, and freeze drying (Chen et al. 2015). The main aspects to consider for the selection of the drying techniques are the production scale and the purpose for which the dried biomass is intended (Show et al. 2013, Show et al. 2014).

Rotary drying is based on the use of a sloped rotating cylinder, also known as rotary dryer. The algae is dried by the movement of the rotating cylinder and the contact with a heated gas (<https://feeco.com/rotary-dryers>).

Spray drying is a process which includes liquid atomization, gas mixing and drying from liquid droplets (Shelef et al. 1984). Atomized water droplets are sprayed down into a vertical tower together with hot gases. The drying process only takes few seconds and the dry product is removed from the bottom of the tower. Although being a very efficient method, cells can be ruptured through the high-pressure atomization process and product quality might be affected (Show et al. 2015).

Vacuum-shelf drying is performed in air-tight vessels. Through vacuum pumps, the humidity and pressure inside the chamber are reduced. This leads to lower atmospheric pressure, which allows quicker drying of the microalgae. It is a suitable drying method for

heat-sensitive products, thus for microalgae used in nutraceutical and food industry, since it protects its nutrients and bioactive compounds from any heat damage (Parikh 2015).

Oven drying involves a hot air oven, commonly used at temperatures around 60 °C. The samples need to be dried for at least 12 hours (Cheirsilp & Torpee 2012, Guldhe et al. 2014). In order to obtain the dry weight of inorganic particles, i.e. ashes, oven-dried samples can undergo incineration, i.e. a drying procedure at a temperature of 450 °C.

Freeze drying, also known as **lyophilization**, is a low temperature dehydration process (Ratti 2008). This process applies on frozen samples, and occurs under vacuum at low temperatures (-40 °C to -80 °C). By doing so, ice undergoes sublimation, i.e. direct conversion from solid to vapour, avoiding the liquid form. The process includes three main steps: (1) freezing, (2) primary drying (sublimation) and (3) secondary drying (desorption). During lyophilization, cells are dried without rupturing the cell wall (Guldhe 2014). This drying process ensures product stability even at room temperature and is widely used in the food industry (Milledge & Heaven 2013).

2.4.1.2. Cell counting

Cell counting under a microscope represents the most common direct method for cell density measurements. An aliquot of the culture is transferred to counting chambers, consisting of a glass slide gridded with one or two large squares of a given surface area. These squares are internally divided into smaller squares, facilitating the counting task. After pipetting a known volume of a microalgae sample, only the cells inside the squares are counted (Figure 9). Since each square corresponds to a given volume, cell density can be easily calculated.

Figure 9. Overview of cell counting in a cell chamber.

Suspensions need to be diluted enough to avoid cell overlapping on the grid and ensure uniform distribution (Grigoryev 2013).

2.4.2. Indirect methods

In most phototrophic organisms, chlorophyll *a* (chl *a*) is a crucial pigment for the conversion of light energy into chemical energy. This allows measurements based on its absorbance (2.4.2.1.) and fluorescence (2.4.2.2.) for estimation of cell density and physiological state, respectively.

2.4.2.1. Optical density

Optical density (OD) measurements are a common, rapid and non-destructive approach to evaluate microbial growth (Toennies & Gallant 1949, Shuler & Kargi 2005). It is considered as a useful method for indirect measurement of biomass in algae cultures. Using a suitable standard curve, cell density can be directly related to absorbance of light in a microalgae suspension (Griffith et al. 2011). Nevertheless, for a reliable characterization of microalgae, cell density measurements need to be combined with biomass analysis since size variations or cell agglomerations can interfere in the optical density measurements. Optical density measurements can be performed using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Light wavelengths used for chl *a* determination are 680 nm and 750 nm (Griffith et al. 2011).

The spectrophotometer measures the intensity of light after passing through a sample (I), and compares it to the intensity of light before it passes through the sample (I_0). The I/I_0 ratio is called transmittance, and is usually expressed as a percentage (%T). The absorbance, A , is based on the transmittance, according to Beer-Lambert law (Swinehart 1962):

$$A = -\log_{10}(1/T)$$

The amount of absorbed light is proportional to the cell density in suspension by using a standard curve (Griffiths et al. 2011).

2.4.2.2. Chlorophyll fluorescence induction Kinetics (OJIP test)

Chlorophyll fluorescence reflects the energetic behaviour of the photosynthetic system. Measurement of chlorophyll *a* (chl *a*) fluorescence constitutes one of the oldest approaches to investigate photosynthesis (Kautsky & Hirsch 1931, Papageorgiou & Govindjee 2004). Nowadays, it has become an important tool for the monitoring of photosynthetic processes and the analysis of the physiological state of photosynthetic organism (<https://handheld.psi.cz/products/aquapen-c-and-aquapen-p/>).

Chlorophyll fluorescence induction kinetics can be measured with a Pulse-Amplitude-Modulation (PAM) fluorometer using a OJIP monitoring program. PAM fluorometer contain blue and red LED emitters, which can deliver light intensities of up to $3000 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-2}$. Blue light at 455 nm is used for chlorophyll excitation, while red-orange excitation light (620 nm) is intended for cyanobacteria (<https://handheld.psi.cz/products/aquapen-c-and-aquapen-p/>).

Chlorophyll fluorescence induction kinetics rely on the light-dependent photosynthesis reaction (Figure 10). The light-dependent photosynthetic reaction takes place in the thylakoid membrane of chloroplasts, the organelles that conduct photosynthesis. The main structure responsible for this part of photosynthesis comprises: (a) two reaction centres, located in the photosystem II (PS_{II}) and photosystem I (PS_I), and (b) an electron transport chain, mainly consisting of plastoquinone A (Q_A), plastoquinone B (Q_B), cytochrome and free plastoquinone (PQ). Both photosystems hold a number of pigments able to collect light, and a special pair of chlorophyll molecules at their core, i.e. reaction centre. Once light reaches the reaction centre of PS_{II}, one photon is absorbed by the chlorophyll, which loses one electron. This electron migrates from Q_A to Q_B and through the electron transport chain until reaching the photosystem I (PS_I) and the PQ pool. In PS_I, another electron is boosted to a high energy level through light excitation. This whole process leads to the reduction of NADP⁺ to NADPH and to the synthesis of ATP. The chlorophyll molecules in the reaction centres regain the lost electrons by the splitting of a water molecule, which releases an oxygen molecule (Finch et al. 2014).

Figure 10. Light-dependent photosynthetic reactions in the thylakoid membrane of chloroplasts. (source: <https://www.khanacademy.org/science/ap-biology/cellular-energetics/photosynthesis/a/light-dependent-reactions>)

The OJIP test reflects three reduction processes of the electron transport chain of the light-dependent photosynthesis reaction. In the dark-adapted state, all photosynthetic reaction centres and molecules of the electron transport chain (Q_A , Q_B and PQ) are in a relaxed state. Relaxed state, also known as “open state”, is when a full complement of electrons is in the ground state and fully oxidized (Küpper et al. 2020). After excitation of the sample with actinic light, i.e. photosynthesis initiating light, a fluorescence induction is observed, known as the Kautsky effect. The chlorophyll fluorescence intensity rises from a minimum level (the O-level), in less than 1 second, to a maximum level (the P – level) via two intermediate steps known as J and I (Stirbet & Govindjee 2011). The name of the test originates from this four levels: O-J-I-P (Figure 11).

Figure 11. A typical OJIP curve, showing the fluorescence intensity of chlorophyll a as a function of time (μs) (Xia et al. 2019).

The O – J rise represents the reduction of the PS_{II} primary acceptor (Q_A) (Boisvert et al. 2006). Once Q_B is also reduced, the “I – level” of fluorescence kinetics has

been reached. Finally, when the PQ pool have also been reduced, the fluorescence quantum yield reaches its peak, the so-called “P –level” (Küpper et al. 2019). In this way, the migration of the electrons through the photosynthetic molecules is reflected in the OJIP fluorescence curve.

PAM fluorometers collect the following main parameters: (1) **basal fluorescence (F_0)**, corresponding to the beginning of the curve (the O portion), defined as the minimum chl *a* fluorescence yield in the dark-adapted state; (2) **maximal fluorescence intensity (F_M)**, defined as the dark-adapted maximum Chl *a* fluorescence yield during the width of the saturating pulse, when the reaction centres are all “closed” (Q_A is reduced); (3) **F_V/F_m ratio**, which corresponds to the maximum light utilisation efficiency of PS_{II} in the dark-adapted state, i.e. the efficiency by which the absorbed photon is trapped by PS_{II} reaction centres.

Further parameters about light absorbance, trapping, electron transport and dissipation can also be studied using PAM fluorometers and represent a useful tool for growth monitoring, since they generally change during the different growth phases of algae cultures. The initial stage of photosynthetic activity of a reaction centre (RC) complex is mainly regulated by the following steps: absorbance of light energy (ABS), trapping of excitation energy (TR), conversion of excitation energy to electron transport (ET) and dissipation energy (DI), the non-trapped energy emitted as heat and fluorescence (Thach et al. 2007).

2.5. LIPIDS FROM MICROALGAE AND THEIR APPLICATIONS

The studies on lipid and fatty acid composition of microalgae started in the 40's (Millner 1948). To date, more than 100 microalgal species have been analysed for lipid composition, which can vary depending on the strain, the origin, and the culture conditions (Teshima et al. 1983, Thompson et al. 1990, Renaud et al. 2002).

Lipids are important components of plant and animal cells, together with carbohydrates and proteins. Lipids include a diverse group of organic compounds, comprising fatty acids, neutral fats, waxes and steroids. The diverse function of lipids originates from a wide diversity in their molecule structure (Fahy et al. 2011). They act as structural components of

Table 1. Valuable lipids produced by diatoms and their bioactivities (Yi et al., 2017).

Lipid class	Valuable composition	Bioactivities
Fatty acids	HTA ¹ (16:3n-3)	Anti-bacterial
	Palmitoleic acid (16:1n-7)	Anti-bacterial
	Stearic acid (18:0)	Antimicrobial
	Remeric acid (20:5n-3)	Antimicrobial
	EPA ² (20:5n-3)	Anticancer, antimalarial, anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory
	DHA ³ (22:5n-3)	Anti-inflammatory
Non-polar lipids	Triacylglycerols	Biofuels
Polar lipids	Glycolipids	Anti-inflammatory, antitumor, antibacterial, antiviral
	Phospholipids	Valuable ingredient in functional foods, cosmetic, pharmaceutical industries
Steroids	24-methylenecholesterol	Anti-inflammatory, antitrypanosomal, anti-mycobacterial
Oxylipins	PUAs ⁴	Antimitotic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial

¹ Hexadecatrienoic acid

² Eicosapentaenoic acid

³ Docosahexaenoic acid

⁴ Polyunsaturated aldehydes

The predominant fatty acids found in diatoms, including the species *Nitzschia palea*, is listed in table 2.

Table 2. Predominant fatty acids (> 10%) found in 19 diatom species with references.

Genus	Species	Predominant fatty acids (> 10 %)	Refs
<i>Amphora</i>	<i>exigua</i>	16:0*, 16:1**	Orcutt & Patterson 1975
	sp.	16:0, 16:1, 20:5 ⁺	Orcutt & Patterson 1975
<i>Biddulphia</i>	<i>aurica</i>	14:0 ^x , 16:1, 20:5	Orcutt & Patterson 1975
<i>Chaetoceros</i>	sp.	14:0, 16:1	Renaud et al. 2002
<i>Cyclotella</i>	<i>cryptica</i>	16:0, 16:1, 16:3***, 20:5	Roessler 1988
<i>Fragilaria</i>	sp.	14:0, 16:1, 20:5	Orcutt & Patterson 1975
<i>Navicula</i>	<i>inserta</i>	16:0, 16:1, 20:5	Opute 1974
	<i>muralis</i>	16:0, 16:1	Opute 1974
	<i>pelliculosa</i>	16:1, 20:5	Orcutt & Patterson 1975
<i>Nitzschia</i>	<i>palea</i>	16:0, 16:1, 20:5	Opute 1974
		16:0, 16:1	Touliabah et al. 2020
	<i>chlosterium</i>	14:0, 16:0, 16:1	Ying et al. 2000
	<i>closterium</i>	16:0, 16:1, 20:5	Orcutt & Patterson 1975
	<i>closterium</i>	16:1, 20:5	Orcutt & Patterson 1975
	<i>frustule</i>	14:0, 16:0, 16:1	Ying et al. 2000
	<i>frustulum</i>	16:0, 16:1	Orcutt & Patterson 1975
	<i>incerta</i>	14:0, 16:0, 16:1	Ying et al. 2000
	<i>longissimi</i>	16:0, 16:1	Orcutt & Patterson 1975
	<i>ovalis</i>	16:0, 16:1	Orcutt & Patterson 1975
<i>Phaeodactylum</i>	<i>tricornutum</i>	16:0, 16:1, 20:5	Orcutt & Patterson 1975
<i>Thalassiosira</i>	<i>psuedonana</i>	14:0, 16:12, 20:5	Orcutt & Patterson 1975

*palmitic acid

** palmitoleic acid

*** palmitlinolenic acid

⁺eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA)

^x myristic acid

Microalgae have long been considered excellent feedstock to produce oils. For example, omega-3 PUFAs (EPA and DHA) play an important role in the nutraceutical sector, used as food supplement for the treatment of arthritis, obesity, Parkinson's disease and heart disease (Fernando et al. 2016, Ramesh Kumar et al. 2019). Indeed, they play a major role in the treatment of inflammation, cardiovascular diseases and fetal brain development (Ramesh Kumar et al. 2019, Adarme-Vega et al. 2012). In the aquaculture sector, microalgae producing omega-3 PUFAs could be used as aquafeed material to improve the quality of aquaculture products.

Another example of promising application of microalgae as feedstock to produce oils concerns the biofuel sector (Scodelaro Bilbao et al. 2017). Their FAs, found in the form of TAGs, can be converted into biodiesel through transesterification reactions.

Given that microalgae produce, amongst many other things, lipids of interest for different industrial applications, it is important to find strategies to maximize their productivity and unlock their potential to the full.

One approach for increasing lipid production in microalgae is biochemical engineering, based on manipulation of nutritional and/or cultivation conditions. As for the nutritional manipulations, nitrogen or phosphorus deprivation is a common method to enhance lipid contents in several microalgae species, including diatoms. As for the cultivation conditions, some examples are: exposure to different light wavelengths and intensities, carbon dioxide levels, temperature, available nutrients, stress due to heavy metals, stress due to salinity (Aratboni et al. 2019).

Other approaches for stimulation of lipid production in microalgae include genetic engineering, modifying gene sequences related to lipid metabolism, or altering their expression (Aratboni et al. 2019).

3. MATERIALS AND METHOD

3.1. LABORATORY CULTURES OF *NITZSCHIA PALEA*

The strains of *Nitzschia palea* which were examined in this study and their location of origin are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Denomination and geographical origin of the three Nitzschia palea strains examined in this study. The strains are deposited in the culture collection of the Spanish Bank of Algae (BEA).

Strain	Species	Geographical origin	Culture collection
BEA 0255B	<i>Nitzschia palea</i>	La Encantadora Dam, La Gomera, Spain	BEA*
BEA 0256B	<i>Nitzschia cf. palea</i>	La Encantadora Dam, La Gomera, Spain	BEA
BEA 0392B	<i>Nitzschia palea</i>	Madre del Agua Ravine-Betancuria Rural Park, Fuerteventura, Spain	BEA

*Spanish Bank of Algae (Gran Canaria, Spain).

Laboratory cultures of *N. palea* were maintained in a thermostated room with a temperature of 20 ± 1 °C under full spectrum light with an incident photon flux density at $25 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and a daily light-dark cycle of 12:12 h light:dark (LD). Light source was placed above the culture flasks. Flasks were randomly placed and the position was changed once a day in order to ensure a homogeneous exposure to light.

Growth experiments were conducted using a batch culture method in 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks with 270 mL of growth medium (surface-to-volume ratio: 0.5). Cultures were grown in sterile FDMed medium optimized for freshwater diatoms (Gérin et al. 2020). The FDMed medium was prepared following the recipe shown in the appendix, and sterilized using an Autester ST Dry PV III P Selecta autoclave for 30 min at 121 °C.

3.2. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

At the beginning of the experiment (day 0), six biological replicates per *Nitzschia palea* strain were equally inoculated at an initial concentration of 86,000 – 162,000 cells mL⁻¹, and cultured under the same conditions detailed above (3.1).

Follow-up measurements of cell growth were conducted every two to three days using direct and indirect methods. Cell counting with a Thoma chamber under an inverted microscope (direct method) was chosen as the method of reference to outline the growth curves of the three strains. Optical density and basal fluorescence measurements (indirect methods) were performed in parallel with cell counting for comparison purposes. Morphometric measurements of cell length and width were also performed at key data points of the growth curve, allowing estimation of biovolume.

Biomass harvesting consisted in triplicate sample aliquots at two data points of the growth curve, one during the exponential growth phase (cultures A), at day 9, and the other during the stationary growth phase (cultures B), at the end of the experimental period (day 26). An aliquot of 10 mL culture underwent a two-step drying procedure to obtain the dry biomass weight (60 °C, overnight) as well as the organic and inorganic composition (450 °C, for 4 hours). An aliquot of 100 mL culture was stored at – 20 °C and then freeze-dried. Lipid extraction was performed using 100 mg of freeze-dried biomass. Lipid content and fatty acid profile were determined using gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (GC-MS) techniques.

Figure 13. Overview of the experimental design. D_n: day of culture; DP: data point; exp.: exponential growth phase; stat.: stationary growth phase; MQ: Milli-Q; OD_n: optical density at a wavelength of n nm; F₀: basal fluorescence; PAM: Pulse-Amplitude-Modulation; GC-MS: gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry..

3.3. FOLLOW-UP MEASUREMENTS OF BATCH CULTURES

3.3.1. Sampling

Culture aliquots for growth studies were collected twice or thrice a week under a laminar flow hood using sterile material. Cells were gently detached from the bottom surface of the Erlenmeyer flasks with a cell scraper and a 6 mL aliquot was sampled after a thorough homogenization of the culture by pipetting up and down. A 2.5 mL subaliquot was 2-fold diluted with Milli-Q water and kept at room temperature for further measurements (3.3.3.1., 3.3.3.2. and 3.3.3.3.). Another 2.5 mL subaliquot was 2-fold diluted with an alkaline Lugol's solution (final concentration: 1%) and stored at 4 °C for further use (3.3.2.).

During the acclimatization and exponential growth phases, culture aliquots for growth studies were collected from the triplicate cultures A until biomass harvesting at day 9. In parallel, cultures B were shaken to simulate the stress undergone by cultures A during the sampling process. Once the biomass from cultures A was harvested (day 9), culture aliquots for growth studies were collected from the triplicate cultures B, until final biomass harvesting at day 26.

3.3.2. Biovolume estimation

Length (l) and width (w) of a minimum of fifteen cells per sample were measured using LAS V3.7.0 software (Leica Application Suite) coupled to an inverted microscope with a 63x objective lens. Mean biovolume (V) was then calculated using a prolate spheroid (ellipsoid) model:

$$V = 4/3 \pi a b^2$$

Where a is the major semi-axis, calculated as l/2, and b is the minor semi-axis, calculated as w/2.

3.3.3. Growth monitoring of batch cultures of *Nitzschia palea*

3.3.3.1. Direct method: Cell counting

Cell concentration of the batch cultures was determined by cell counting under an inverted microscope (Leica DMI3000 D series) equipped with a 20x objective lens, using a Thoma counting chamber of 0.1 mm depth (Figure 14, a). Cell counting was performed in duplicate squares with 1 mm² surface (volume: 10⁻⁴ mL) (Figure 14, b).

Figure 14. (a) photo of the Thoma counting chamber of 0.1 mm depth; (b) zoom on the duplicate squares with 1 mm² surface used for cell counting.

Cell concentration per mL was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Cell concentration (cells mL}^{-1}\text{)} = N \times 10^4 \times f$$

Where N is the number of cells counted per 1 mm² square and f is the dilution factor of the sample prior to counting.

3.3.3.2. Indirect method: Optical density with spectrophotometer

Optical density (OD) measurements of *N. palea* cultures were carried out using a Shimadzu UV-1900 UV-VIS spectrophotometer at two wavelengths, 680 and 750 nm. 2 mL samples were carefully homogenised by pipetting up and down into a 4 mL transparent cuvette prior to OD measurements. The absorbance of light without sample was determined using FDMed medium as blank sample (OD set to 0).

The wavelengths at which the algae samples were measured were chosen in accordance with the absorption spectrum of chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*), one of the main pigments involved in photosynthetic activity (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Light absorbance spectra of plant photosensitive pigments as a function of wavelengths (nm) ranging from the UV region to the far-red region (source: <http://www.ledgrowlightshq.co.uk/chlorophyll-plant-pigments>)

3.3.3.3. Indirect method: *In vivo* chlorophyll fluorescence

Determination of *in vivo* chlorophyll fluorescence of *N. palea* cultures was carried out using the Induction Kinetics (OJIP) mode of an AquaPen-C (AP-C) 100 fluorometer. The instrument was set as follows: blue excitation light at a wavelength of 450 nm, measuring flash pulse at 30% (f pulse = $0.009 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), saturating pulse at 50% (F pulse = $1,500 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and actinic light pulse at 30% (A pulse = $300 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). Prior to OJIP measurements, 2 mL samples were dark-adapted in 4 mL transparent cuvettes for 15 minutes (Consalvey et al. 2005), and then carefully homogenised by pipetting up and down. A minimum of three measurements for each sample was performed.

In this study, F_0 values of dark-adapted samples were obtained at $50 \mu\text{s}$ and used as an indirect method for cell density measurements. Along with this, F_v/F_m ratio was used as an indicator of the photophysiological state of the cultures. Further photosynthetic parameters regarding absorbance, dissipation and electron transfer (ABS/RC , TR_0/RC , ET_0/RT and DI_0/RC) were also obtained through OJIP measurements.

3.3.3.4. Growth rate and doubling time

Maximum growth rate (μ_{\max}) and doubling time of *Nitzschia palea* strains in batch cultures were calculated using the portion of the growth curve with the steepest slope (day 4 – day 7):

$$\mu_{\max} (\text{day}^{-1}) = \ln(N_2/N_1)/(t_2 - t_1)$$

$$t_{1/2} (\text{days}) = \ln(2)/\mu_{\max} (\text{day}^{-1})$$

Where:

N_1 = cell concentration (cells mL⁻¹) at t_1 (day 4);

N_2 = cell concentration (cells mL⁻¹) at t_2 (day 7).

3.3.4. Biomass harvesting and quantification

Prior to harvesting, cells of *Nitzschia palea* were gently detached from the bottom surface of the Erlenmeyer flasks using a cell scraper under sterile conditions. Cultures were thoroughly mixed by pipetting up and down to ensure a homogeneous suspension of the cells in the water column.

For biomass determination of *Nitzschia palea*, samples were harvested at two points of the growth curve (day 9 and day 26) and dried using two different procedures (3.3.4.1. and 3.3.4.2.).

All the weight measurements were performed using a COBOS analytical balance (accuracy: 0.1 mg).

3.3.4.1. Oven-dried weight

A 10 mL aliquot of each culture suspension was transferred in a pre-weighed crucible under a sterile hood. The samples were then dried in a Trade Rey02 drying oven at 60 °C overnight and weighed again to obtain the dry weight (DW w/ ashes). The dry biomass was then placed in a Nabertherm B180 stove for 4 hours at 450 °C. The remaining biomass, i.e. the “ashes”, were weighed after cooling down at 60 °C in the drying oven. The dry weight without ashes (DW w/o ashes) was then calculated as follows:

$$\text{DW w/o ashes (mg)} = \text{DW w/ ashes (mg)} - \text{ashes (mg)}$$

DW and ashes amounts (mg) were expressed per mL of culture.

3.3.4.2. Lyophilized weight

A 100 mL aliquot of each culture suspension was transferred in a pre-weighed sterile container under a laminar flow hood. Subsequently, the samples were stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight and then lyophilized using a Labconco FreeZone⁶. The lyophilization was carried out for 96 hours at a temperature between $-48\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-52\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a pressure of 0.120 mbar. The lyophilized biomass was weighed to obtain the freeze-dried weight (mg) and was expressed per mL of culture.

3.3.4.3. Productivity

The maximum productivity of *Nitzschia palea* strains in batch cultures was calculated between day 4 and day 7 (maximum growth rate) as follows:

$$\text{Productivity (g DW L}^{-1}\text{ d}^{-1}) = (N_2 - N_1) / (t_2 - t_1)$$

where N_2 was the biomass amount (DW w/ ashes, g) per L culture obtained at t_2 (day 7) and N_1 was the biomass amount (DW w/ ashes, g) per L culture obtained at t_1 (day 4).

3.3.5. Determination of lipid content and fatty acid profile

Total lipid and fatty acid profile of *Nitzschia palea* were assessed using triplicate lyophilized samples harvested at day 9 and day 26 of the experiment.

The procedural steps of this part of the work follow the protocols described by Folch et al. (1957) and Christie et al. (1982), and are schematized in Figure 16

Figure 16. Overview of the procedural steps for total lipid and fatty acid determination, according to Folch et al., 1957 and Christie et al., 1982.

3.3.5.1. Total lipid determination

Total lipids were extracted using the method described by Folch et al. (1957).

The organic solvent used for the lipid extraction was a combination of chloroform and methanol with a ratio 2:1 v/v, respectively.

First, 100 mg of freeze-dried algal biomass was mixed with 5 mL of chloroform-methanol with 0.01 % butylated hydroxyl toluene (BHT). In order to obtain the crude extract, this mixture was homogenized with an IKAT25 digital Ultra-Turrax for 5 minutes.

Subsequently, purification steps started by the addition of 2 mL of a saline solution (KCl 0.88 %) with following centrifugation (5 min at 2000 rpm). The upper layer containing salts and aqueous methanol was discarded, and the lower layer containing chloroform-methanol with the extracted lipids was filtered.

Filtration was performed using a funnel with a filter paper filled with ca. 20 g of sodium sulphate anhydride. The obtained filtrate was finally evaporated with nitrogen gas and the mass of the lipid residue was determined gravimetrically (total lipids).

Total lipids were then stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until further extraction (3.3.5.2.).

3.3.5.2. Fatty acid determination

Fatty acids were recovered from the total lipid extracts according to the methodology described by Christie et al. (1982).

An aliquot of 10 mg of only one replicate per strain was used. When the lipid residue was below 10 mg, two replicate samples of the same strain were combined.

In the first step, transmethylation of the lipids was performed by adding 1 mL toluene with BHT (100 mg L^{-1}) and 2 mL of 1 % sulphuric acid in methanol. After shaking and sealing each sample with nitrogen gas, each sample was incubated for at least 16 hours in darkness at $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to remove oxygen from the sample vials and minimize lipid oxidation.

After incubation, 3.5 mL MQ water and 4 mL of the extraction solvent hexane-diethylether (ratio 1:1, v/v) with 0.01 % BHT were added. After 5 min centrifugation at 2000 rpm, the upper phase of hexane-diethylether was separated from the lower phase, mixed with 3 mL of the salt solution KHCO_3 (2 % in MQ H_2O) and vigorously shaken. After centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 5 minutes, the upper phase was filtered through an Aminopropyl (NH_2)

cartridge from Sep-Pak® RC (500 mg). The filtrate was dried down with nitrogen gas and weighed. The dried residue was dissolved with 1 mL per 40 mg fatty acids.

The final identification and quantification of fatty acids was carried out using the Agilent Technologies 7820A gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry under the analytical conditions described by Izquierdo et al. (1990). The fatty acids were separated using a Supercowax 10 column (30 m x 0.32 mm, 0.25 µm i.d.), and with helium as carrier gas. The pressure was constant at 100 kPA, while the temperature rise from initial 170 °C to final 220 °C (temperature rise of 2 °C/min). The detection of the peaks was carried out with a flame ionization detector (FID) and the working method SPLIT. The temperature of the injection and flame ionization stations was of 250 °C. Fatty acids were finally identified by comparison with characterized external standards.

3.3.6. Statistical analysis

The statistical tests performed for the evaluation of the results were the following: the two-sample t-test for dependent samples and the two-factor analysis of variance (ANOVA). All statistical analysis were performed with Excel software (Microsoft Office).

The two-sample t-test for dependent samples was applied on the following datasets: (a) cell counting on fresh and preserved algae samples (4.1.), (b) cell density estimation with direct and indirect measurements methods (4.3. and 4.4.) and (c) F_v/F_m values from the exponential and the stationary growth phase (4.5.).

ANOVA tests were performed for the comparisons between strains and also between growth phases within a given strain, and concerned the following datasets: (a) biomass parameters (ash content, lyophilized and heat dried biomass, biomass per cell and biomass per biovolume), and (b) lipid content. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) among growth phases or strains were further analysed by pairwise comparison t-test.

4. RESULTS

4.1. CORRELATION BETWEEN CELL COUNTING WITH FRESH AND PRESERVED ALGAE SAMPLES

Cell density of the cultures of *Nitzschia palea* during the batch experiment was measured over time using a Thoma counting chamber under an inverted microscope (Cell counting). Figure 17 shows the correlation between cell density measurements of fresh samples and of their corresponding preserved samples. Cell counting of fresh samples was conducted right after the sampling time. Cell counting of the same samples preserved with 1 % lugol was conducted after several weeks of storage at 4 °C (6 – 0 weeks).

Figure 17. Cell density measurements obtained through cell counting of fresh algae samples versus preserved algae samples (1% lugol at 4 °C after several weeks) of the following *Nitzschia palea* strains: (a) BEA0255B, (b) BEA0256B and (c) BEA0392B. Cell countings of fresh algae samples were conducted right after the collection time. Cell countings of the lugolized algae samples was conducted after 6 – 10 weeks storage at 4 °C. Intercept was set at zero.

Cell density using fresh and preserved algae samples positively correlated for all *N. palea* strains (BEA 0255B, BEA 0256B and BEA 0392) with a slope very close to 1, R^2 values > 0.96 and a statistical significance of $P > 0.4$ (t-test; BEA0255B $P = 0.78$, BEA0256B $P = 0.62$ and BEA0392B $P = 0.48$).

4.2. GROWTH STUDIES

Figure 18 shows cell density over time for the three strains of *Nitzschia palea* (BEA 0255B, BEA 0256B and BEA 0392B) in batch cultures during the experimental period (26 days).

Figure 18. Cell density as a function of time for the *Nitzschia palea* strains (a) BEA 0255B, (b) BEA 0256B and (c) BEA 0392B. Cell density is expressed in natural logarithm scale; time spent in culture is expressed in number of days.

The curves of the graphs in Figure 18 all follow the same pattern: (1) lag phase from day 0 to day 4, (2) exponential phase from day 4 to day 17, and (3) stationary phase from day 17 on. Senescence phase was not observed for any of the strains during the experimental period.

Maximum growth rate and productivity were calculated during the exponential phase between the two data points where growth curves showed the steepest slope. In the experimental conditions of our study, this corresponded to day 4 and day 7 of cultivation for all the three *N. palea* strains tested. The BEA 0392B strain had the highest maximum growth rate ($\mu_{\max} = 0.29 \text{ day}^{-1}$), with a minimum doubling time ($-DT_{\min}$) of 2.41 days, followed by BEA 0256B ($\mu_{\max} = 0.23 \text{ day}^{-1}$, $DT_{\min} = 3.19 \text{ days}$) and BEA 0255B ($\mu_{\max} = 0.21 \text{ day}^{-1}$, $DT_{\min} = 3.29 \text{ days}$) (Table 4).

The BEA 0256B ($0.23 \pm 17 \% \text{ (RSD)} \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$) and BEA 0392B ($0.23 \pm 12 \% \text{ (RSD)} \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$) strains showed the lowest productivity ($0.23 \pm 12 \% \text{ (RSD)} \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$), while BEA 0255B showed the highest with $0.41 \pm 3 \% \text{ (RSD)} \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (Table 4).

The average cell densities during the stationary phase (days 17 – 26) of the BEA 0255B, BEA 0256B and BEA 0392B were of $1.5 \times 10^6 \pm 7\% \text{ (RSD)}$, $1.6 \times 10^6 \pm 8 \% \text{ (RSD)}$, and $1.3 \times 10^6 \pm 6 \% \text{ (RSD)}$, respectively. The results of maximum growth rate (μ_{\max}), minimum doubling time (DT_{\min}), initial and final cell density and productivity of each strain are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Initial cell density (CD_i , cells mL^{-1}), maximum growth rate (μ_{\max} , day^{-1}), minimum doubling time (DT_{\min} , days), final cell density (CD_f , cells mL^{-1}) and productivity ($\text{g L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$) of the *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA 0255B, BEA 0256B and BEA 0392B. The CD_i values indicate cell concentration at seeding time of the experiment (day 0). The μ_{\max} values and their corresponding DT_{\min} were calculated between days 4 and 7 of cultivation. The CD_f values correspond to the arithmetic mean of cell concentration during the stationary phase (days 17 – 26, $n = 5$). RSD: relative standard deviation (%).

<i>Nitzschia palea</i> strain	CD_i (day 0) (cells mL^{-1})	μ_{\max} (days 4 – 7) (day^{-1})	DT_{\min} (days 4 – 7) (days)	CD_f (days 17 – 26) (cells mL^{-1})	Productivity (days 4 – 7) ($\text{g L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$)
BEA 0255B	$1.6 \times 10^5 \pm 13 \% \text{ (RSD)}$	$0.21 \pm 11 \% \text{ (RSD)}$	$3.29 \pm 11 \% \text{ (RSD)}$	$1.5 \times 10^6 \pm 7\% \text{ (RSD)}$	$0.41 \pm 3 \% \text{ (RSD)}$
BEA 0256B	$1.3 \times 10^5 \pm 11 \% \text{ (RSD)}$	$0.23 \pm 26 \% \text{ (RSD)}$	$3.19 \pm 23 \% \text{ (RSD)}$	$1.6 \times 10^6 \pm 8\% \text{ (RSD)}$	$0.23 \pm 17 \% \text{ (RSD)}$
BEA 0392B	$0.91 \times 10^5 \pm 4 \% \text{ (RSD)}$	$0.29 \pm 15 \% \text{ (RSD)}$	$2.41 \pm 0.14 \% \text{ (RSD)}$	$1.3 \times 10^6 \pm 6\% \text{ (RSD)}$	$0.23 \pm 12 \% \text{ (RSD)}$

No statistical difference between the maximal growth rate of the *N. palea* strains could be demonstrated (ANOVA, $P = 0.18$). On the other side, the difference in the productivity was significant between BEA 0255B and BEA 0256B (t-test, $P < 0.05$) and BEA 0255B and BEA 0392B (t-test, $P < 0.05$).

4.2.1. Differences between *Nitzschia palea* strains

The three *Nitzschia palea* strains had different cell sizes at the beginning of the experiment (day 0), being BEA 0255B strain the one with the largest cells and BEA 0392B the one with the smallest cells (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Microscopic observation of the cells of the *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA 0255B (a), BEA 0256B (b) and BEA 0392B (c). Leica DM6000 B, DIC mode (20x, 14x).

The cells of the BEA 0392B strain, being the smallest compared to the other two strains, were in worst condition by the end of the experiment. Overall, the cells of the three strains started losing adherence on the 10th day of cultivation, and from then on, they did not attach as much to the bottom of the culture vessels (Erlenmeyer flasks). This can be seen in the pictures (c) and (d) of Figure 20, corresponding to day 16 and day 21 of cultivation.

Figure 20. Pictures of the bottom part of the culture flasks containing *Nitzschia palea* BEA0255B after (a) 4, (b) 9, (c) 16 and (d) 21 days of cultivation.

Morphometric measurements (length, width and estimated biovolume), of the three strains of *N. palea* during the experimental period are reported in Table 5.

Table 5. Morphometric measurements (length, width and biovolume) of the *Nitzschia* palea strains BEA 0255B, BEA 0256B and BEA 0392B at day 0, 4, 9, 17 and 26 of cultivation. X: mean, SD: standard deviation, n: number of measurements.

Day	Strain	Length (μm)	Width (μm)	Biovolume (μm^3)
Min – max ($X \pm \text{SD}$)				
0	BEA 0255B	28.2 – 33.7 (30.7 \pm 1.4) (n=30)	4.2 – 5.8 (5.1 \pm 0.3) (n=30)	286 – 539 (416 \pm 58) (n=30)
	BEA 0256B	23.1 – 28.4 (25.8 \pm 1.2) (n=30)	4.4 – 6.3 (5.6 \pm 0.4) (n=30)	264 – 583 (422 \pm 66) (n=30)
	BEA 0392B	13.8 – 18.2 (16.1 \pm 1.2) (n=27)	4.1 – 6.0 (5.3 \pm 0.5) (n=27)	132 – 314 (238 \pm 43) (n=27)
4	BEA 0255B	27.0 – 33.4 (29.8 \pm 1.6) (n=31)	4.2 – 5.3 (4.8 \pm 0.2) (n=31)	273 – 450 (359 \pm 39) (n=31)
	BEA 0256B	22.7 – 28.0 (25.3 \pm 1.3) (n=37)	4.3 – 6.1 (5.4 \pm 0.4) (n=37)	248 – 489 (390 \pm 62) (n=37)
	BEA 0392B	13.3 – 18.8 (15.7 \pm 1.1) (n=33)	4.0 – 5.5 (4.9 \pm 0.4) (n=33)	128 – 249 (198 \pm 29) (n=33)
9	BEA 0255B	25.0 – 32.3 (29.5 \pm 1.6) (n=45)	4.2 – 5.9 (5.0 \pm 0.4) (n=45)	226 – 570 (392 \pm 68) (n=45)
	BEA 0256B	23.2 – 29.5 (26.1 \pm 1.4) (n=45)	4.2 – 6.5 (5.4 \pm 0.5) (n=45)	247 – 588 (406 \pm 78) (n=45)
	BEA 0392B	14.1 – 17.9 (16.1 \pm 1.0) (n=45)	4.1 – 6.1 (5.2 \pm 0.4) (n=45)	145 – 340 (233 \pm 41) (n=45)
17	BEA 0255B	27.7 – 33.5 (29.5 \pm 1.3) (n=36)	4.1 – 5.2 (4.8 \pm 0.2) (n=36)	248 – 447 (356 \pm 37) (n=36)
	BEA 0256B	21.3 – 28.4 (24.8 \pm 1.8) (n=36)	3.7 – 5.6 (5.2 \pm 0.4) (n=36)	163 – 418 (348 \pm 45) (n=36)
	BEA 0392B	13.2 – 18.5 (15.9 \pm 1.3) (n=35)	3.6 – 5.8 (5.2 \pm 0.5) (n=35)	109 – 323 (227 \pm 40) (n=35)
26	BEA 0255B	24.5 – 33.8 (29.3 \pm 2.0) (n=41)	4.0 – 5.6 (4.9 \pm 0.4) (n=41)	229 – 551 (370 \pm 73) (n=41)
	BEA 0256B	21.8 – 27.9 (25.0 \pm 1.5) (n=52)	4.3 – 7.2 (5.4 \pm 0.6) (n=52)	223 – 734 (392 \pm 97) (n=52)
	BEA 0392B	14.2 – 17.8 (16.1 \pm 0.9) (n=40)	4.4 – 6.1 (5.3 \pm 0.3) (n=40)	167 – 302 (238 \pm 31) (n=40)

The estimated biovolume values reported in Table 5 were calculated using the formula of an ellipsoid “prolate spheroid” ($\frac{4}{3} \pi a b^2$), which most closely resembles the form of a pennate diatom cell.

As shown in Table 5, BEA 0255B and BEA 0256B were morphometrically more similar to each other; BEA 0392B was smaller in length and volume since the beginning of the experiment. Still, the difference in length between all the strains were significant (ANOVA, $P < 0.05$).

Cell size of the three *N. palea* strains slightly decreased throughout the length of the experiment, although the decrease was not significant for any of the strains (ANOVA, $P = 0.16$).

4.3. CORRELATION BETWEEN CELL DENSITY AND OPTICAL DENSITY (OD₆₈₀, OD₇₅₀)

Figure 21 shows the correlation between cell density and optical density measurements for the three strains of *Nitzschia palea*. The three strains were cultivated in three replicate batch cultures and the correlation was run separating the data points into two distinct groups, one corresponding to the exponential growth phase (day 4 –17, Figure 21 a – c) and the other corresponding to the stationary phase (day 17 – 26, Figure 21 d – f).

Figure 21. Linear correlation between optical density at 680 nm (OD_{680} , $AU\ cm^{-1}$) and cell counting (cell density, $cells\ x\ 10^4\ mL^{-1}$) of the *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA0255B (a)(d), BEA0256B (b)(e) and BEA0392B (c)(f) at their exponential phase (day 4 – 17, a – c) and stationary phase (day 17 – 26, d – f). ○ = day 4, ◇ = day 7, △ = day 9, ✱ = day 14 and □ = day 17.

Cell density and optical density correlated positively and significantly (t-test, $P < 0.001$) in the exponential growth phase (day 4 – 17) with R-squared values higher than 0.89.

Very poor correlation was found between cell density and optical density during the stationary growth phase (day 17 – 26), with R-squared values lower than 0.37 (t-test, $P < 0.001$).

The same applied to the data measured with OD_{750} : high correlation between cell density and optical density only during the exponential phase, with R-squared values higher than 0.86 (Figure 22). Overall, the R-squared values were slightly lower than the ones from the OD_{680} correlation with cell density, still the difference was not statistically significant (t-test, $P < 0.001$).

Figure 22. Linear relationship between OD₇₅₀ and cell density ($\times 10^4$) of the *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA0255B (a)(d), BEA0256B (b)(e) and BEA0392B (c)(f) at their exponential phase (day 4 – 17, a – c) and stationary phase (day 17 – 26, d – f). ○ = day 4, ◇ = day 7, △ = day 9, ✱ = day 14 and □ = day 17.

4.4. CORRELATION BETWEEN CELL DENSITY AND BASAL FLUORESCENCE (F_0)

Figure 23 shows the relationship between cell density measurements of the three strains of *Nitzschia palea* and their basal fluorescence (F_0) during the experimental period. Two

separate linear correlation tests were run, one using the data points corresponding to the exponential growth phase (day 4 –17, Figure 23 a – c), the other with the data points corresponding to the stationary growth phase (day 17 – 26, Figure 23 d – f).

Figure 23. Linear relationship between F_0 and cell density ($\times 10^4$) of the *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA0255B (a)(d), BEA0256B (b)(e) and BEA0392B (c)(f) at their exponential phase (day 4 – 17, a – c) and stationary phase (day 17 – 26, d – f). \circ = day 4, \diamond = day 7, \triangle = day 9, \ast = day 14 and \square = day 17.

During the exponential phase (Figure 23, a – c), cell density and basal fluorescence presented significant positive linear regression for all the strains tested, with R-squared values higher than 0.90 (t-test, $P < 0.001$).

On the contrary, very poor correlation between these two parameters was found in the stationary growth phase (Figure 23, d – f), with R-squared values below 0.4 (t-test, $P < 0.001$).

4.5. PHOTOSYNTHETIC EFFICIENCY – OJIP MEASUREMENTS

Figure 24 shows the measurements of maximum photosynthetic efficiency of PSII, i.e. F_V/F_M , throughout the length of the batch culture experiment for the three *Nitzschia palea* strains examined in this study.

Figure 24. Maximum photosynthetic efficiency of PSII (F_V/F_M) of the *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA0255B (a), BEA0256B (b) and BEA0392 (c) from day 2 – 26 of cultivation.

F_v/F_m values of the BEA 0255B and BEA 0256B batch cultures varied between 0.5 and 0.6 throughout the experimental length (0.64 ± 0.04 and 0.61 ± 0.04 , $n=10$). The difference between the F_v/F_m values of the exponential and stationary phase was not significant for neither of these strains (t-test, $P > 0.18$).

On the other side, F_v/F_m values of the BEA 0392B batch culture started to decrease after day 7 of cultivation, and a second slight decrease can be observed in the graph by the time the batch cultures were entering the stationary growth phase, varying between 0.4 and 0.5 values. The standard deviation was higher compared to the other two strains (0.52 ± 0.07 , $n=10$). However, a $P < 0.05$ (t-test) proved significant difference between F_v/F_m values at the exponential phase and F_v/F_m values at the stationary phase of the BEA 0392B batch cultures.

Further data about more detailed photosynthetic activity regarding photosynthetic light-absorbance, -use, -dissipation, and electron transport (ABS/RC, TR₀/RC, ET₀/RC and DI₀/RC) were also obtained through OJIP-measurement and showed in Figure 25.

Figure 25. Photochemical parameters derived from the OJIP-measurements of the *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA0255B (a), BEA0256B (b) and BEA0392B (c) during the experimental length. ABS/RC: absorption flux per reaction center (RC), DI0/RC: dissipated energy flux per RC, ET0/RC: electron transport flux per RC and TR0/RC: trapping flux per RC.

Changes in the energy fluxes (ABS/RC, TR₀/RC, ET₀/RC and DI₀/RC) during the length of the batch cultures experiment were not particularly appreciable, i.e. there were no considerable differences of these parameters for the different growth phases.

4.6. CHARACTERIZATION OF THE BIOMASS OF *NITZSCHIA PALEA* BATCH CULTURES

4.6.1. Dry biomass

Figure 26 compares the biomass obtained at the exponential phase (day 9 of cultivation) with the biomass obtained at the stationary phase (day 26 of cultivation) of each *N. palea* batch culture triplicate. The inorganic fraction, i.e. ashes, is also represented in the Figure 26.

Figure 26. Dry biomass and inorganic fraction (mg/mL) of the three *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA 0255B (a), BEA 0256B (b) and BEA 0392B (c) at their exponential and stationary phase. ■ inorganic fraction, ■ dry biomass without inorganic fraction.

Each *N. palea* batch culture triplicate had a biomass gain of $0.0002 \pm 0.0001 \text{ g mL}^{-1}$ from the exponential to the stationary growth phase.

The amount of inorganic fraction did not differ between the *N. palea* strains (ANOVA, $P = 0.9$). At the exponential phase an average amount of $57 \pm 1 \%$ ashes was measured, while at the stationary phase it was an average amount of $46 \pm 5 \%$. However, the difference between the ash fraction in the exponential and stationary phase was not significant for any of the strains (ANOVA, $P > 0.15$)

4.6.2. Lyophilized versus oven-dried weight

The comparison between dry biomass with inorganic fraction (DW-w/), dry biomass without inorganic fraction (DW-w/o) and lyophilized biomass (LYO) of all *Nitzschia palea* strains at their exponential (day 9 of cultivation) and stationary phase (day 26 of cultivation) is showed in Figure 27.

Figure 27. Dry weight of the *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA0255B (a)(d), BEA0256B (b)(e) and BEA0392B (c)(f) at their exponential phase (day 4 – 17, a – c) and stationary phase (day 17 – 26, d – f). DW-w/: dry weight with inorganic fraction, DW-w/o: dry weight without inorganic fraction and LYO: lyophilized dry weight.

Dry biomass with inorganic fraction and lyophilized biomass showed very similar amounts in all three *N. palea* strains. The difference between both weights is the smallest in the strain BEA 0392B. While the difference is slightly bigger in the other two strains, the standard deviation in the samples from the exponential phase are higher (RSD > 13 %). Nevertheless, the difference between heat dried biomass and lyophilized biomass was only significant for the samples from the stationary phase of the BEA 0255B strain (t-test, $P < 0.05$). The amount of dry biomass without inorganic fraction was clearly lower in all three *N. palea* strains, verifying that lyophilized biomass does still contain inorganic fractions.

4.6.1. *Nitzschia palea* biomass characteristics during growth phases

Size characteristics of the three *Nitzschia palea* strains are showed in Table 6 for cells from the exponential phase (day 9) and from the stationary phase (day 26). The data corresponds to biomass with ashes.

Table 6. Size characteristics ($\mu\text{g/mL}$, $\mu\text{g/cell}$ and $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{m}^3$) of the *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA 0255B, BEA 0256B and BEA 0392B at day 9 (exponential phase) and day 26 (stationary phase). The data corresponds to “biomass with ashes”. X: mean, s: mean error

Culture day	<i>Nitzschia palea</i> strain	BIOMASS $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$	BIOMASS per CELL $\mu\text{g cell}^{-1}$	BIOMASS per BIOVOLUME $\mu\text{g } \mu\text{m}^{-3} (\times 10^5)$
9	BEA 0255B	3890 \pm 198	0.0061 \pm 0,0010	1.55 \pm 0.26
	BEA 0256B	3553 \pm 490	0.0055 \pm 0,0012	1.36 \pm 0.30
	BEA 0392B	3000 \pm 325	0.0079 \pm 0,0016	3.39 \pm 0.69
26	BEA 0255B	3843 \pm 78	0.0024 \pm 0,0002	0.64 \pm 0.05
	BEA 0256B	3,426 \pm 221	0.0019 \pm 0.0001	0.48 \pm 0.03
	BEA 0392B	3,286 \pm 12	0.0023 \pm 0.0003	0.96 \pm 0.11

The biomass differences between exponential and stationary phase as well as between the strains were not significant (ANOVA, $P > 0.05$). On the contrary, observing the biomass per cell, differences between growth phases were significant (ANOVA, $P = 0.02$), while differences between strains were also not significant (ANOVA, $P = 0.38$). Comparison between the biomass per biovolume showed no significant differences between exponential and stationary phase, neither between strains (ANOVA, $P > 0.05$)

4.6.2. Lipid content

The average lipid % dry weight of the three *N. palea* strains during exponential and stationary phase is showed in Table 7.

Table 7. Average lipid % of dry weight of the *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA 0255B, BEA 0256B and BEA 0392B during the exponential and stationary phase. X: mean, s: mean error.

<i>Nitzschia palea</i> strain	Average Lipid % dry weight ($X \pm s$)	
	Exponential phase	Stationary phase
BEA 0255B	11 \pm 4	6 \pm 1
BEA 0256B	10 \pm 1	6 \pm 1
BEA 0392B	9 \pm 2	8 \pm 2

The lipid content of all three *N. palea* strains was higher during the exponential phase. The average lipid portion (%) dry weight of BEA 0255B, BEA 0256B and BEA 0392B during the exponential phase was of 11 \pm 4, % 10 \pm 1 % and 9 \pm 2 % respectively. In comparison, during the stationary phase, the portion was lower: BEA 0255B with 6 \pm 1 %, BEA 0256B with 6 \pm 1 % and BEA 0392B with 8 \pm 2 % dry weight. However, the differences between exponential and stationary phase and between the strains were not significant (ANOVA, P > 0.05).

4.6.3. Fatty acid profile

The fatty acid profiles of the three *Nitzschia palea* strains at their stationary phase are represented in Figure 28. Since the fatty acid analysis could not be carried out in all three of the strain replicates, the results are only an estimation.

No fatty acids could be detected in the *Nitzschia palea* samples from the exponential phase, since the concentration was below the limit of detection.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 28. Fatty acid profile of the *Nitzschia palea* strains BEA 0255B (a), BEA 0256B (b) and BEA 0392B (c) at their stationary phase.

The highest concentration of fatty acids detected in all *Nitzschia palea* strains was palmitic acid (16:0) and palmitoleic acid (16:1n-7). The strains BEA 0255B and BEA 03092B had also very high Eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) (20:5n-3) amounts (14 – 22 %). While the EPA concentration of the strain BEA 0256B was slightly lower (6 %), it contained almost double the amount of palmitic acid compared to the other two strains (48 %). Smaller portions (< 10 %) of saturated fatty acids: myristic acid (14:0), margaric acid (17:0), stearic acid (18:0); and unsaturated fatty acid: Arachidonic acid (20:4n-6), Docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) (22:6n-3), Elaidic acid (18:1n-9), Linolelaidic acid (18:2n-6), vaccenic acid (18:1n-7) and 16:1n-5 were identified in all three strains. Further fatty acids were detected in trace amounts around 1 % and therefore not taken into account.

The percentage of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids were of 33 % and 67 % for BEA 0255B, 52 % and 48 % for BEA 0256B and 30 % and 70 % for BEA 0392B, respectively.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. PERTINENCE OF LUGOL'S SOLUTION FOR SAMPLE PRESERVATION

Preservation agents are necessary in order to minimise cell deterioration and morphological changes occurring after sampling, and thus to ensure sample's quality. Lugol's solutions (from 1 up to 5 %) (Sano et al. 2020) have long been used for the preservation of microplankton samples (Kemp et al. 1993). Compared to other widely used preservatives such as formaldehyde and glutaraldehyde, they have the advantage to be less hazardous for human health (Andersen & Thronsen 2003).

Lugol's solutions are composed of iodine and potassium iodide (Sano et al. 2020) and can be prepared in acidified, alkaline or neutral forms. They preserve microplanktonic cells by fixating them while the iodine acts as a bacteriostatic, avoiding the digestion of the cells by bacteria. Nonetheless, the effectiveness of Lugol's solutions for long-term storage of the samples is unclear (Sano et al. 2020) and taxa-specific, and thus needed to be tested for the diatom species in this study. According to some studies (dalcon environmental 2018), Lugol's solution dissolves hard structures such as coccoliths and diatom frustules and is therefore not ideal for the long-term preservation of some algae taxa. Morphological changes using Lugol's solution were also reported in the literature, e.g. in planktonic protozoa (Choi & Stoecker 1989) and in the Chrysophyceae species *Monas* sp. (Børsheim & Bratbak 1987). The latter observed that cell volume decreased up to 60 % after 2 weeks of storage in Lugol's solution.

In this study, the samples obtained during the batch culture experiment of the three *Nitzschia palea* strains were preserved in a Lugol's solution in its alkaline form (pH = 8.15) at 1 % for several weeks. All data gathered, a one-to-one relationship was found between cell counting of fresh and preserved algae samples of *N. palea* (slope = 0.99) (Figure 29), with a high correlation ($R^2 = 0.97$, $P = 0.76$, $n = 121$).

Figure 29. Cell density estimation through cell counting of fresh algae samples versus preserved algae samples (1% alkaline Lugol) of *Nizschia palea* BEA 0255B, BEA 0256B and BEA 0392B. Cell counting of fresh algae samples was conducted right after sampling time. Cell counting of the preserved algae samples was conducted 6 – 10 weeks after the cell counting of the fresh algae samples. Intercept was set at zero.

This finding indicates that the quantity of the cells of *N. palea* preserved in the lugolized samples did not suffer significant changes, even after several weeks of storage. Moreover, it was not possible to appreciate any qualitative change in the cells from microscopic observations, apart from a slight yellow coloration. Therefore, *N. palea* cells can be preserved at 4 °C with 1 % Lugol’s solution (final concentration), at least up to four months. This finding allows to postpone cell countings of a given sample of this species without time pressure. Effectiveness of preservation with different Lugol’s concentrations, pH, temperature or longer storage was not tested in this study.

It is worth mentioning that Lugol’s fixation implies cell death, with the arrest of all metabolic processes, including pigment activity. Therefore, indirect measurements of cell density based on fluorescence and absorbance of chlorophyll *a* are not suitable for lugolized samples. These measurements have to be performed on fresh algae samples as early as possible after collection, while the cells remain alive. Postponement would considerably affect the accuracy of the measurements, since living cells undergo physiological and metabolic changes over time, according to their life cycle, including multiplication and death. Furthermore, it should be noted that the iodine in the Lugol’s solution increases the specific weight of the cells, accelerating their settling time (Anderson & Karlson 2017).

While this is an advantage for cell counting under an inverted microscope, it can affect the homogeneity of the samples and thus the spectrometric and fluorometric measurements.

5.2. GROWTH STUDIES

5.2.1. Biovolume analysis

The growth curves of all three *N. palea* strains had a similar pattern consisting in three phases: (1) lag phase, from day 0 to day 4; (2) exponential phase, from day 4 to day 17; and (3) stationary phase, from day 17 to the end of the experiment (day 26). None of the three strains showed a significant drop in cell size during the experimental period (26 days). This is due to the fact that the experimental period was too short to appreciate the inevitable progression into the life cycle that implies cell size reduction (2.2.1.). Consequently, it was not possible to estimate the shrinking rate over time, nor predict the survival time left for these strains.

According to the life cycle of *N. palea* proposed by Bagmet et al. (2020), the morphometric data of this study concerning cell length indicate that the three strains were in the reproductive phase. Anyway, the BEA 0392B strain was in a later stage of its life cycle, close to the lower threshold for sexual reproduction (2.2.1.).

5.2.1. Growth rate

In this study, the maximum growth rate of *N. palea* fell into the range of 0.21 – 0.29 day⁻¹ (0.29 day⁻¹ for BEA 0392B, 0.23 day⁻¹ for BEA 0255B and 0.21 day⁻¹ for BEA 0256B). The growth rates differed up to a factor 1.4 between the strains (not significant). According to Banse (1982), growth rates can differ up to a factor 3 among equal sized cells within a given species.

A previous study by Barnett et al., 2015 reported growth rates in the range of 0.50 – 1.32 day⁻¹ for four pennate diatoms (*Amphora* sp., *Nitzschia* sp., *Proschkinia* sp. and *Navicula incerta*). Compared to that study, our *N. palea* strains showed lower growth rates, which could either be because of intrinsic factors, such as the species itself (e.g. its benthic behaviour), or because of external factors regarding the culture conditions used (temperature, irradiance, culture medium, surface-to-volume ratio, and/or initial cell density).

Interestingly, the smallest strain of this study (BEA 0392B) also showed the highest growth rate. This leads to the hypothesis of the existence of an inverse relationship between cell size and growth rate. This could be in part explained if we consider the general assumption that small organisms reproduce themselves more rapidly than larger ones (Williams 1964). In support to that, a recent study by Morin et al. (2008) found a significant inverse correlation between cell volume and growth rate for 19 diatom species, including *N. palea*. This allometric relationship was also observed in another study on cyanobacteria (Nielsen 2006). In fact, cell size has long been recognised as an important parameter related to growth rate variability (Banse 1976, Blasco et al. 1982, Geider et al. 1986, Langdon 1987, Tang 1995, Raven & Kübler 2002). From our study, it could not be determined whether the faster growth observed for BEA 0392B strain is due to a distinctive phenotype of this particular strain or because it was in a later stage of the life cycle compared to the other two strains.

In order to understand the potential impact of the life cycle stage on the growth rate in *N. palea*, growth studies of BEA 0255B and BEA 0256B should be repeated in the same culture conditions when cells reach the same size as BEA 0392B in this study. If their growth rates increase, it would support the hypothesis of the existence of an inverse correlation between cell size and growth rate. This would mean that the speed of mitotic division would vary during the lifetime of a given strain, all other conditions being equal. As a consequence, comparative growth studies would only make sense between strains having very similar size at the beginning of the experiment.

5.2.1. Productivity

Nitzschia palea is a benthic species; it means that the cells do not live freely in the water column and need a surface on which to attach in order to proliferate. This is why for benthic organisms, the ratio between surface area and volume should be considered for an efficient

productivity estimation. In this study, *N. palea* strains were cultured with 270 mL culture medium into Erlenmeyer flasks (maximum capacity: 1 L) presenting a circular bottom surface of 134.78 cm², leading to a surface-to-volume ratio of 0.5. An increase of the surface-to-volume ratio could lead to improved productivity. This would consist in adapting the cultures to smaller volumes of culture media into vessels like rectangular flasks, laid horizontally to have more surface area on the bottom. These culture vessels would be more appropriate for benthic organisms, but they present the disadvantage of requiring more space in the culture chamber. The culture flasks need to be positioned on a shelf side by side, to ensure a homogeneous exposure to the light source situated on the top of them. Nowadays, while numerous photobioreactors exist for planktonic species, photobioreactors for benthic organisms still need to be further developed. Some recent studies on horizontal photobioreactors, open promising perspectives for the improvement of benthic microalgae cultivation (Dogaris et al. 2015, Zhu et al. 2018).

5.3. INDIRECT METHODS FOR CELL DENSITY ESTIMATION

5.3.1. Optical density (OD₆₈₀ and OD₇₅₀)

Results from this study indicate that cell density of *N. palea* can be estimated using optical density (OD) during the exponential phase of growth, using the equation given by the correlation straight line. This finding is in accordance with previous studies on other microalgae, such as *Isochrysis galbana* (Gómez et al. 2015) and *Nannochloropsis oculata* (Krishnan et al. 2015). Cell density estimation through OD measurements allows to skip the laborious step of cell counting under the microscope.

Results from this study also indicate that this indirect method is not appropriate for cultures in their stationary growth phase. This could be a consequence of culture aging, which affects pigment content and efficiency and can lead to inaccurate measurements (Griffiths et al. 2011). Indeed, pigment content, on which OD measurements rely, is not constant over time. As previously described by Stevenson et al. (2016), it is advisable to calibrate the

spectrophotometer as a function of the changes in cell size and/or pigment content expected during growth. In this way, it is possible to express the OD data as absolute numbers. By conducting calibrations of OD against cell density for different cell sizes and pigment concentrations, species-specific standard curves covering the entire growth cycle could be generated and allow correlation between OD and cell density in the stationary phase.

A further issue about measurement through pigment-dependent methods, such as OD, is the fact that non-viable cells can still possess their photopigments (Veldhuis et al. 2001). Consequently, non-viable cells can potentially be detected by the spectrophotometer, interfering with the measurements and adding incorrect data about the growth monitoring of the microalgae cultures. A possible approach could be to include a viability test, once the microalgae enters stationary phase, or remove non-viable cells by centrifugation.

As mentioned before, diatom cells change in size and pigmentation during their life cycle. At this point, it is necessary to make a distinction between growth phases (exponential and stationary) and life cycle stages. Concerning the growth phases, the growth curves were consistent for the three *N. palea* strains, i.e. they underwent exponential and stationary phases at the same time. Concerning the life cycle stages, morphometric analyses showed that BEA 0392B strain had significantly lower cell size than the other two strains, indicating that it was in a later stage of the life cycle. Considering this, it would be expected that smaller cells have less pigments at their disposal (Maraóón et al. 2007), leading to a change of the correlation between OD and cell density. Anyway, when gathering the data of the three *N. palea* strains altogether, a good linear correlation could still be found during the exponential growth phase ($R^2 = 0.91$, $n = 45$). This suggests that life cycle stage does not interfere in this correlation for *N. palea*, at least in the cell length range of this study. This allows using the same formula to calculate cell density through OD, without having to consider cell size or life cycle stage of each *N. palea* strain. A future approach should include comparison between direct and indirect measurement methods of more *N. palea* strains in the same culture conditions, and ideally at different life cycle stages, to test if the same equation is applicable to the *N. palea* as a whole.

In this study, optical density was measured both at 680 nm (OD₆₈₀) and at 750 nm (OD₇₅₀). Both measurements gave a positive linear correlation with cell countings, with OD₆₈₀ measurements having slightly higher R-squared value. The difference between OD₆₈₀ and OD₇₅₀ data was not significant. Some previous studies (Dillschneider 2014, Griffith et al.

2011) preferred the use of OD₇₅₀ over OD₆₈₀ for growth monitoring. Griffith et al. (2011) reported that the absorbance at 680 nm is more affected than the one at 750 nm by the common changes in pigment content throughout a growth cycle in microalgae. Results from this study suggest that the interferences that can arise using OD₆₈₀ do not have a major impact for this species, and thus either OD₆₈₀ or OD₇₅₀ can indifferently be used for cell density estimation of *N. palea*.

5.3.2. Basal fluorescence (F₀)

In this study, basal fluorescence (F₀) measurements during the exponential growth phase also resulted as an effective indirect method for growth monitoring of *N. palea*. This finding is in accordance with a previous study on different diatom species conducted by Barranguet & Kromkamp (2000).

As it was the case for OD determination, the fluorometric method was found to be not suitable for cultures in their stationary growth phase. F₀ measurements depend on the PS_{II} photophysiology, which can be altered during stationary phase due to nutrient limitation (Forster & Martin-Jezequel 2005, Bender et al. 2014).

In the same fashion as for optical density, non-viable cells can also alter F₀ measurements (Veldhuis et al. 2001), which is why further approaches should include viability tests or remove non-viable cells prior to measurements.

As for the OD, the correlation formula for F₀ against cell density is applicable for all three *N. palea* strains, regardless of their size/life cycle stage. A future study including more *N. palea* strains at different life cycle stages would allow to test if this formula is also applicable to other strains of this diatom species (all other conditions being equal).

5.3.3. Photosynthetic efficiency

The photosynthetic efficiency of algae cultures can be estimated measuring the F_v/F_m ratio, i.e. the maximum light utilisation efficiency of photosystem II (PS_{II}). Studies regarding biological oceanography have widely accepted F_v/F_m to be influenced by nutrient stress, i.e.

limitation or starvation (Parkhill et al. 2001). Falkowski (1992) reported a correlation between nutrient stress and the decline of key proteins of the reaction centres, with a consequent inactivation of PS_{II} and changes in the chemical composition. Therefore, higher F_v/F_m values are expected in nutrient-replete cultures, while F_v/F_m values are expected to decrease under nutrient stress (Parkhill et al. 2001, Kolber et al. 1988, 1990, 1993, Flaming 1998, Kromkamp & Peene 1999).

In this study, the nutrient uptake by the cells was not measured. Still, it is known that nutrient availability decreases over time in batch cultures, being one of the reasons for cells to enter the stationary growth phase. F_v/F_m values measured in *N. palea* during this study were between 0.5 and 0.6 for the three strains during the exponential growth phase (nutrient-replete condition), in accordance with the literature (Ting & Owens 1994, Kromkamp et al. 1998). Following the correlation between nutrient availability and photosynthetic reaction centres (Falkowski 1992), a decrease in the F_v/F_m ratio was expected during the stationary growth phase (nutrient stress condition). In this study, this decrease was somewhat appreciable for BEA 0392B, but still not remarkable. Indeed, F_v/F_m values did not decrease by more than 22 % for BEA 0255B and 32 % for BEA 0256B, and this decrease was punctual and not maintained over time. On the other side, BEA 0392B showed a decrease of 61 % from the highest F_v/F_m value (day 4) to the lowest value at day 26.

In a previous study on *Chlorella* by Malapascua et al. (2014), a decrease in F_v/F_m value of 36 %, together with a decrease in relative electron transport rate (rETR) and light saturation coefficient (E_k), were efficient indicators of physiological stress due to nutrient limitation. In this study, the fluctuating trend of F_v/F_m over time, together with the lack of rETR and E_k measurements, do not allow concluding the same.

Further considerations on this issue are detailed as follows.

As reported by Parkhill et al. (2001), the relationship between F_v/F_m values and the growth phases breaks down when phytoplankton acclimates to nutrient limitation. This could have been the case for the *N. palea* strains in this study. The photosynthetic apparatus may not have suffered a major decline over time and, consequently, the transition from the exponential (nutrient-replete) to the stationary (nutrient-limited) phase was not reflected into F_v/F_m measurements.

Another aspect to consider when measuring the photosynthetic activity is the complications due to the complexities of the microphytobenthos, as discussed by Consalvey et al. (2005).

Benthic organisms are more difficult to homogenise prior to the measurements, and might settle down during the process, leading to potential inaccuracies. All in all, the photosynthetic process, photophysiology and especially the behaviour of migratory diatoms need to be further studied (Consalvey et al. 2005).

In summary, F_v/F_m was not a suitable parameter for physiological state determination of *N. palea* and did not contribute to the growth monitoring in this study. The other photosynthetic parameters evaluated in this study were likewise impractical for this purpose.

It is worth mentioning that PAM-fluorometry relies on the utilization of light by chlorophyll *a*. Signals from non-viable cells, which still possess their photopigments, can lead to incorrect results. This problem can be solved sorting viable cells prior to measurement, or using alternative methods which do not depend on fluorescence. Oxygen production and CO₂ are also used to monitor photosynthetic activity (Malapascua et al. 2014) and can be measured through oxygen microelectrodes and radio-labeled ¹⁴C probes, respectively (Consalvey et al. 2005). According to Malapacua et al. (2014), PAM fluorescence data should be accompanied by a second measurement method for more reliability.

5.4. BIOTECHNOLOGICAL INTEREST OF *NITZSCHIA PALEA*

5.4.1. Biomass amount

In this study, the biomass of *N. palea* was dried using two different methods: heat drying (60° C) and lyophilization. The biomass yield as “dry weight with ashes” obtained by heat drying did not significantly differ from the “freeze-dried weight” obtained by lyophilisation. This finding indicates that the two drying procedures are equally valid for biomass recovery, at least in terms of amount. Nevertheless, the biochemical composition of the biomass might be altered by the drying method used. For instance, lipids are susceptible to oxidization and hydrolysis, and special care should be taken in sample handling. Züllig et al. (2019)

recommended restricting the storage of samples to a period that is as short as possible, at temperatures below $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Lyophilisation operates at considerably lower temperatures than heat drying, and is therefore more suitable for lipid determination.

The ash content of the harvested biomass was between 39 – 57 % of dry biomass and did not differ significantly between the two growth phases in any of the three strains. Compared to other microalgae such as *Chlorella* sp. (ash content: 6.36 %) (Phukan et al. 2011), and *N. oculata* (ash content: 24.47 %) (Sukarni et al. 2014), the ash content in our *N. palea* strains was very high. A high ash content in algae biomass is considered a disadvantage for biotechnological applications. For example, in the field of biodiesel production, ashes contribute to poorer fuel quality and to the decrease of heating values (Vassilev & Vassileva 2016). Ash-forming elements appear in biomass as salts bounded to the carbon structure or as mineral particles from cultivation environment and introduced into the biomass during the harvesting process (Sukarni et al. 2014). For this reason, as reviewed by Krishan et al. (2015), a centrifugation step is generally included in biomass harvesting procedures, ensuring the separation of the microalgae biomass from (almost) the vast majority of residues from the culture medium. This step was skipped in this study, so the high ash content present in the biomass may be partly due to residues from the culture medium. For future approaches, it is advisable to separate the harvested biomass from the culture medium for a more accurate determination of the ash content. This might probably lead to lower ash content percentage and also allow a better comparison between the different growth phases.

Even though the three strains presented significant differences in cell size (cell length and biovolume) during the experimental period, differences in biomass amounts were not significant and they can be treated as a whole.

The biomass concentrations (biomass with ashes) obtained in this study were very high compared to the literature, ranging from 3.1 – 3.8 g L⁻¹. A previous study on *N. palea* conducted by Touliabah et al. (2020) reported a biomass concentration for this species of 0.11 – 0.25 g L⁻¹. Krishan et al. (2015) reported biomass concentrations in the range of 0.6 g L⁻¹ for *Nannocloropsis oculata*, and Renuka et al. (2013) in the range of 0.9 g L⁻¹ for *Calotrix* sp..

Regarding differences in biomass between growth phases, they were not significant. Although cell density doubled or tripled at day 26 compared to day 9, the biomass amount did not follow the same pattern for any of the strains (day 9: 3.1 – 3.5 g L⁻¹, day 26:

3.3 – 3.8 g L⁻¹). At this point, it is important to consider the diatom life cycle, which include cell size reduction over time. For this reason biomass concentrations were normalized per cell and per biovolume for each strain in both growth phases. By doing so, the biomass per cell resulted significantly higher at the exponential phase than at the stationary phase. Considering this, it should be evaluated if it is effective to wait until stationary phase for harvesting in order to get more biomass or if it is industrially more productive to harvest at an earlier growth phase saving time, space and labour.

Further studies should include biomass harvesting at more points of the growth curve, in order to determine the optimal harvesting time. These studies should focus not only on biomass amounts, but also on biomass composition, and in particular to the lipid and fatty acid contents at these data points.

5.4.2. Lipid content

Microalgae cells are able to produce lipid amounts up to 50 – 86 % of dry weight (DW) depending on the species and the culture conditions (Vassilev & Vassileva 2016). Diatoms generally produce an average lipid content of 25 % DW (Levitan et al. 2014, Cerón Garcia et al. 2006), but can produce up to 45 % DW (Hu et al. 2008, Frada et al. 2013). Among others, the growth phase of a microalgae culture is an important factor in lipid production. During the stationary growth phase, lipid production is generally favoured. One of the reasons is that cells have less nutrients available in the culture medium, which leads to a reduction in cell division and primary metabolism, and a stimulation in the production of secondary metabolites. Some classes of lipids (e.g. for energy storage) are included in the latter (Nigam et al. 2011, Zhu et al. 1997, Opute 1974).

It is worth mentioning that substantial oil accumulation almost always requires stress conditions, as reported by Li-Beisson & Peltier (2013). The nutrient limitation during the stationary growth phase can be considered as a stress factor, but stress can also be induced through targeted nutrient limitations. A recent study about the effect of various stresses on lipid production of microalgae showed an increase in lipid content in 14 different species through nitrogen, phosphorus and sulphur limitation, as well as changes in the light intensity, the temperature and the salinity (Shi et al. 2020 and references within). However, the

mechanism is not fully understood yet and the regulation of the lipid biosynthesis under stressful conditions needs to be further studied in diatoms (Obata et al. 2013).

In this study, *N. palea* did not follow the general trend described above: lipid content was slightly lower during the stationary phase with respect to the exponential phase, although not significant. This was also reported in a previous study by Cortois de Viscose et al. (2012) on the diatom species *Nitzschia* sp., *Amphora* sp. and *Proschkinia* sp..

Moreover, the lipid amounts obtained in this study were lower compared to other studies for similar microorganisms (Vassilev and Vassileva 2016, Levitan et al. 2014, Cerón Garcia et al. 2006, Hu et al. 2008, Frada et al. 2013, Chen 2012). For example, the amounts obtained in this study (5 – 15 % DW) were at least 2-fold lower than the ones reported by Chen (2012) for 12 species of diatoms (30 – 45 % DW).

All in all, high lipid content could not be detected in any of the *N. palea* cultures of this study. According to Li-Beisson & Peltier (2013), the ability to produce high lipid amounts is generally species or strain specific, rather than genus specific. This could explain the low lipid values obtained in this study against data from the literature about diatoms.

Before stating that the strains of *N. palea* cultivated in this study are not suitable for lipid production at industrial scale, some factors including culture conditions and extraction methods should be further studied.

For instance, concerning culture conditions, inclusion of stress factors in the culturing practices should also be considered, as supported by numerous examples in the literature. Cultivation of microorganisms in nutrient-starvation media could be a more efficient way for lipid boost than nutrient limitation that is usually observed in batch cultures over time. Nevertheless, drastic reduction in nutrient availability (e.g. nitrogen starvation) can lead to a severe drop in the growth rate of diatoms (Hildebrand et al. 2012, Frada et al. 2013). While lipid production might be favoured in stressful culture conditions, lower growth rates do not benefit the applicability of diatoms for industrialization.

Concerning the lipid extraction methods, it is worth mentioning that several protocols have been described in the literature (Ranjith Kumar et al. 2015). These protocols differ in terms of extraction efficiency, selectivity and lipid recoveries. In this study, lipids were extracted following the original Folch method (Folch et al. 1957). Nevertheless, the modified protocol proposed by Matyash et al. (2008) has been described as more efficient and more accurate

for lipidomic profile determination. For future studies, it would be interesting to re-extract part of the same biomass with the Matyash method and compare the results with the ones obtained in this study.

5.4.3. Fatty acid composition

The fatty acid (FA) composition of *Nitzschia palea* in this study can only be considered as a preliminary study, since no triplicates could be analysed. Also, the biomass obtained during the exponential growth phase (day 9) was not analysed due to insufficient dry residues of the lipidic fractions. Therefore, results concerning the FA composition in this study refer to one replicate of one datapoint only (day 26, stationary phase). In order to deepen the studies on FA composition of *N. palea*, future approaches should include the extraction of higher amounts of biomass.

The FA profile of microalgae is mostly composed of FAs with C16 – C18 chain length, being the most common FAs the following: palmitic (16:0), stearic, palmitoleic (16:1n-7), oleic, linoleic and linolenic acids (Liu & Liu 2017). In diatoms, the most common FAs are the following: palmitic acid (16:0), palmitoleic acid (16:1n-7), eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA, 20:5n-3) and myristic acid (14:0) (Levitan et al. 2014).

In this study, the major fatty acids (FAs) produced by the three *N. palea* were: palmitic acid (18 – 41 %) and palmitoleic acid (12 – 25 %). EPA constituted a major FA for BEA 0255B and BEA 0392B (13 – 21 %), while it was produced in lower amounts by BEA 0256B (almost 5 %). Other FAs found in lower amounts (< 10 %) were: myristic acid, oleic acid, docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) and arachidonic acid. Linoleic and linolenic acid were also found, with concentrations below 1 %. The results from this study are in accordance with a previous study conducted by Touliabah et al. (2020) on *N. palea*, where palmitic acid (41.13 %) and palmitoleic acid (29.25 %) represented the main FAs. Also, the amounts of minor FAs from Touliabah et al. (2020), i.e. myristic acid (9 %), stearic acid (2.32 %), oleic acid (3.22 %), and linoleic acid (0.48 %), were in accordance with this study.

Comparison with other diatom species also show similarities with results from this study. Ying et al. (2000) found palmitoleic acid (14 – 26 %), palmitic acid (25 – 33 %), EPA

(3 – 7 %) and myristic acid (1 – 6 %) as major FAs in eight different marine diatom species, including three from the *Nitzschia* genus (*N. frustule*, *N. incerta* and *N. chlosterium*).

Results from this study are also similar to those reviewed by Levitan et al. (2014) for the following diatom species: *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Navicula inserta*, *Nitzschia closterium*, *Cyclotella cryptica*, *Amphora* sp. and *Nitzschia palea* (Table 2, paragraph 2.5.).

It is worth mentioning that extraction and preservation of samples can influence the fatty acid profile. In this study, *N. palea* samples were stored at –20 °C in reason of the unavailability of freezing devices operating at lower temperatures. This might have affected the results on the lipid profile of the strains. According to Jüttner (2001) and Pohnert (2002), palmitoleic acid and EPA may be artifact products of the storage and/or extraction method used. They reported that unsaturated fatty acids are not found in their free form in relevant amounts in healthy diatom cells, and can arise from lipid catabolism induced during the extraction process by enzymatic and chemical processes after sampling (Kong et al. 2018). In order to prevent lipid catabolism, Züllig et al. (2019) proposed rapid sample processing and storage at temperatures below –80° C. Storage time should ideally be short, considering the potential risk of lipid oxidization and hydrolysis (Züllig et al. 2019).

Contemplating the FA profiles of the *N. palea* strains of this study, different industrial applications could be approachable in the future. Among the fatty acids found at major concentration, EPA has long been of great interest for industrial applications in the nutraceutical sector. This omega-3 polyunsaturated FA has showed significant health benefits with anti-oxidative, anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer properties and thus has led to an increased consumption as dietary supplements. In addition to its application as food supplement for human consumption, EPA also founds interesting application as feed material in the aquaculture industry. Indeed, successful cultivation of oysters, scallops and mussels depends on omega-3 FAs from microalgal feedstock (Adarme-Vega et al. 2012).

The high concentration of palmitic and palmitoleic acids found in this study could also be exploited for industrial purposes. Both FAs show beneficial health effects, reducing cardiovascular diseases, insulin sensitivity and cholesterol metabolism amongst others (Table 1, paragraph 2.5.). Also, palmitic acid is used in the cosmeceutical sector for the preparation of personal care products such as soaps.

In the biofuel industry, the properties of the fatty acid esters that form the biodiesel determine its quality (Knothe 2005). Biodiesel is a mixture of fatty acid esters with a backbone chain

of mostly 16 to 18 carbon atoms. The chain length of the backbone, degree of unsaturation and chain branching are major factors influencing the biodiesel quality (Deshmukh et al. 2019). They can affect the levels of emissions, cold flow, oxidative stability, viscosity and lubricity among others (Knothe 2005, Durret et al. 2008). A biodiesel with optimal characteristics should contain: (a) high levels of mono-unsaturated FAs (MUFAs), such as palmitoleic acid (16:1) and oleic acid (18:1), and (b) low levels of saturated FAs and polyunsaturated FAs (PUFAs) (Knothe 2005, McCormick et al. 2001).

While polyunsaturated FAs like EPA and DHA are highly valued in the nutraceutical industry, in the oil industry they are considered as a disadvantage for their lower oxidative stability, being necessary the addition of antioxidants (Sotana de Souza et al. 2020). In this study, the percentage of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids in *N. palea* was of 38 % \pm 10 and 62 % \pm 10, respectively. Similar results were reported in a recent study by Sotana de Souza et al. (2020) for another diatom species, *Scenedesmus* sp., (22 % saturated FAs and 78 % unsaturated FAs). Among the unsaturated FAs, MUFAs and PUFAs were present in equal amounts. Overall, the fatty acid profile of the *N. palea* cultures in this study did not seem to have the best characteristics for biodiesel applications. While the MUFA palmitoleic acid was one of the major FAs produced by the three strains in this study, the presence of similar amounts of the saturated FA palmitic acid counteracted this advantage. Also, BEA 0255B and BEA 0392B are even less exploitable as biodiesel source, considering the relatively high amounts of the PUFA EPA. The results from this study corroborate the considerations by Levitan et al. (2014, p.119), stating that “no natural FA profile can suffice the production of an ideal biodiesel”.

All in all, the *N. palea* strains evaluated in this study could have potential application in various sectors of the industry. More accurate studies on the lipid profiles should be developed in future approaches to have a more comprehensive view of the biotechnological value of these strains.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

Conclusion

This Master's thesis studied the growth of three native strains of *Nitzschia palea* from the Canary Islands in the laboratory, contributing to a better understanding of various practical and procedural aspects related to its cultivation and downstream process.

Preservation with 1 % Lugol at 4 °C was proven to be effective for *N. palea*, allowing cell counting and size measurements to be performed several weeks after sampling without deterioration.

Optical density and basal fluorescence were suitable alternatives to cell counting for cell density estimation during the exponential phase of growth, allowing faster execution of the daily laboratory work. However, fluorometric determination of photosynthetic parameters, such as F_v/F_m , was not useful for estimating the physiological state of the cultures.

Although biomass amounts were found to be relatively high compared to the literature, growth rates and productivities were rather low. Strain performance at the laboratory scale might have been affected by size reduction inherent to the progression of diatoms into the life cycle.

Both biomass amounts and lipid content did not show significant differences between the growth phases of *N. palea*, suggesting that it is not necessary to wait until the stationary phase for biomass harvesting.

In conclusion, this Master's thesis included a first attempt of lipid characterization of the benthic diatom *N. palea* from the Canaries, which opens the perspective of potential biotechnological applications.

Perspectives

Given the potential industrial applicability of the *Nitzschia palea* strains of this study, optimization studies on the cultivation techniques and downstream processing should be included in future approaches, to increase their productivity and lipid recovery.

First, cultivation material and experimental conditions need to be addressed and optimized for *N. palea* specifically. For instance, the culture vessel should be more adapted to the benthic character of this species, focusing on higher surface area instead of water column capacity. Also, different experimental conditions need to be applied for increased growth rates and/or lipid production.

Furthermore, growth studies on the same *N. palea* strains at different life cycle stages should be performed. This would include cultivation over a longer experimental period, in order to cover their entire life cycle. Also, exploitation of the sexual phase of the life cycle might contribute to genetic improvement of the species. These studies would lead to a deeper understanding of the impact of the diatom life cycle on the growth rate and productivity.

As for the suitability of indirect methods for growth monitoring, cultivation of more strains in the same culture conditions would corroborate the findings of this study and generalize the conclusions for the *N. palea* species as a whole.

Another aspect that needs further development is the study of the optimal harvesting time for the obtention of biotechnologically relevant biomass. In order to do so, biomass collection should be performed at more points of the growth curve and subsequently be analysed for its lipid content and fatty acid profile.

Last, but not least, further studies should also address sample storage and lipid extraction procedures with the aim of improving the quality of the output products.

7. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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8. APPENDIX

FDMed (Freshwater medium optimized for diatoms) (Gérin et al. 2020)

Stock solutions

Table 8. Preparation of stock solutions of FDMed medium. Gérin et al. 2020

Stock solutions	Component	Stock concentrations
Solution 1	Tris-HCL pH 7.5	1 M
Solution 2	NaNO ₃	1 M
Solution 3	Na ₂ SiO ₃	4.5 M
Solution 4	K ₂ HPO ₄	100 mM
Solution 5	NaHCO ₃	100 mM
Solution 6	H ₃ BO ₃	1 mM
Solution 7	CaCl ₂ x 2H ₂ O	100 mM
Solution 8	MgSO ₄ x 7H ₂ O	100 mM
Trace metals	MnCl ₂ x 4 H ₂ O	900 mg L ⁻¹
	CuSO ₄ x 5 H ₂ O	12.5 mg L ⁻¹
	ZnSO ₄ x 7 H ₂ O	110 mg L ⁻¹
	CoCl ₂ x 6 H ₂ O	50 mg L ⁻¹
	NaMoO ₄ x 2 H ₂ O	31 mg L ⁻¹
	Na ₃ VO ₄	90 mg L ⁻¹
	FeCl ₃ x 6 H ₂ O	15.75 mg L ⁻¹
	Na ₂ EDTA	21.8 mg L ⁻¹

Medium preparation (1 L)

Table 9. Protocol for the preparation of FDMed medium (1 L).

Stock solution	Volume (mL)	Final concentration
Distilled water	748	-
Solution 1	10	10 mM
Solution 2	5	5 mM
Solution 3	1.184	5.33 mM
Solution 4	3.333	0.33 mM
Solution 5	20	2 mM
Solution 6	10	0.01 mM
Solution 7	2.5	0.25 mM
Solution 8	10	1 mM

The solutions 1 – 8 are added to a 1 L vessel with distilled water one by one. Once all the solutions have been added, the pH is adjust to 7.5 with HCL 1N and the vessel is filled up to 1 L with distilled water. The FDMed medium is then sterilized using a Autester ST Dry PV III P Selecta autoclave for 30 min at 121 °C.

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